

Atlantic Ecosystems Assessment, Forecasting & Sustainability

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Version History

Version	Authors	Summary of changes	Date
1	R. Lopes et al.	D4.5	Dec 2022
2	R. Lopes et al.	D4.7	Feb 2026

1 Executive summary

This Deliverable aims at describing the main activities carried out within the scope of AtlantECO Work Package 4 relative to task 4.2. The objective of Task 4.2 is to generate new observations about microbiomes, plastics and the plastisphere. It was implemented by partners EMBL, USP, EMBRC-ERIC, EMSO-ERIC, CEA, AWI, CNRS, CSIR, FTO, FURG, NIOZ, NOC, MBA, SU, SZN, UCT, UFSC, UFSCar, UniLIV and UP through six activities:

- Flagship cruises (Subtask 4.2.1)
- All Atlantic Ocean Sampling Day (Subtask 4.2.2)
- Sail-4-Science (Subtask 4.2.3)
- Continuous Plankton Recorder (Subtask 4.2.4)
- Genomics, Carbon and Plastic analysis of Moored Sediment Trap samples (Subtask 4.2.5)
- Third party cruises (Subtask 4.2.6)

Progress was achieved to various degrees by the six Subtasks, two of which (Subtasks 4.2.1 Flagships and 4.2.6 Third party cruises) saw several delays due to covid-19 restrictions, and two others (Subtasks 4.2.2 AA-OSD and 4.2.3 S4S) were rescheduled to ensure the success of our engagement with external partners and citizens.

Task 4.2 has benefited from activities covered by task 4.1, by means of two deliverables scheduled and completed during the first reporting period (M0-M20):

- D4.1 “AtlantECO Handbook of Standards and Best Practices (version 1)” was delivered with a few months delay to incorporate survey results and feedback from participants to AtlantECO’s Webinar on standards and best practices (May 2021). It is available on Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4897861>).
- D4.2 “AtlantECO Handbook of Standards and Best Practices (version 2)” was delivered with a few months delay to incorporate the latest materials from AtlantECO’s training course in South Africa (May 2022) and other activities. It is available on Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4897860>).

Handbook guidelines have been applied with success in flagship cruises belonging to Task 4.2, including the Tara Mission Microbiomes expedition, Eugene Seibold cruises, expeditions along the Brazilian coast, and a RV Alpha Crucis expedition in the SW Atlantic off Brazil.

In addition, WP4 completed all milestones scheduled during the first reporting period (M0-M20), which also positively impacted activities belonging to Task 4.2:

- MS01 “Port calls schedule established for the first 2 years” was completed, and the schedule is publicly available on the AtlantECO website (<https://www.atlanteco.eu/expeditions>).
- MS02 “AtlantECO standard protocols workshop” was completed, and both the workshop proceedings (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4275504>) and the resulting deliverable D4.1 are publicly available on Zenodo.
- MS09 “First South Atlantic CPR campaign” was completed, and the campaign summary report is publicly available on Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6023403>).
- MS10 “Workshop aimed at harmonising quality control and analysis methods for the South Atlantic CPR survey.” was completed online and the resulting CPR control and analysis protocols are included in D4.2. A second workshop in person is scheduled for the second reporting period.

A single key exploitable result was produced by Task 4.1. The AtlantECO Handbook of Standards and Best Practices (D4.1 & D4.2) is a compendium of resources and will be consolidated throughout the second and third activity periods of the project (D4.3 & D4.4). A series of Webinars and training materials produced by the European Blue Biobank (EBB), a synergy initiative led by AtlantECO partner EMBRC-ERIC, are also exploited by AtlantECO together with the Handbook.

The Handbook was used to implement several research activities in Task 4.2, notably the flagships and third-party cruises, the All-Atlantic Ocean Sampling Day, the citizen Sail-4-Science, and the Continuous Plankton Recorder (CPR) survey line between Santos and Durban. The Handbook was also exploited by WP4 to implement its Hub & Nodes approach to develop inter-comparable analysis pipelines across the project's imaging and sequencing centres in Europe (CEA & SU), South Africa (UP & UCT) and Brazil (UFSCar & USP). Finally, the Handbook was exploited by WP9's capacity building and training activities, such as the Port Calls of Mission Microbiomes (Sept 2021 - Sept 2022), and AtlantECO's 10-day training course in South Africa (May 2022).

The analysis of molecular (DNA/RNA) legacy samples by partner CEA (Genoscope sequencing centre) is cross-cutting several subtasks and is being coordinated by partners EMBL and CEA. The strategies put in place broadly consist of Illumina metagenome, metatranscriptome, and metabarcoding (18sV9, 18sV4, 16SV4V5) sequencing. So far, the ensemble of the three legacy sample subprojects has allowed generating an average of 644 million pair end reads corresponding to a total of 96.8 Gb of genomic data produced.

For the Atlantic Meridional Transect (AMT), Genoscope has provided 16S and 18S rRNA gene data for samples collected on board AMT23-JR300, AMT24-JR303, AMT27-DY084, AMT28-JR18001, and AMT29-DY110 (a total of 280 samples sequenced). Currently, these data are being processed at PML. 16S rRNA gene data (but no 18S rRNA gene data) will also be made available to the AtlantECO project from AMT19-JC039 and AMT20-JC053. Some samples collected on AMT27-DY084 have been selected for metagenomic and metatranscriptomic sequencing by Genoscope.

The preparation and sequencing of the Plastisphere legacy datasets have been a joint effort across multiple institutes. Genoscope has been sequencing plastisphere metagenomic libraries, and the Instituto Gulbenkian de Ciência (IGC) has been sequencing amplicon libraries. NIOZ technician Maartje Brouwer, Leslie Murphy (MBL), and Giulia Stilo (University of Torino) have been involved in sample processing and library generation. Currently, they have sequenced 63 metagenomes, with 58 to a depth of 50 million reads and 5 to a depth of 250 million reads. These samples are being screened with preliminary analyses, and some samples collected have been earmarked for deeper sequencing.

The NIOZ Team is identifying the polymer types using μ FTIR and μ RAMAN for the samples used to build MG libraries. To date, 94-3D and 94-Euk-specific samples have been sequenced with preliminary analyses in play. Sixty of these are earmarked for fungal ITS amplifications. An additional 100-3D and 100-euk-specific amplicon samples are ready for sequencing, and an additional 80 samples await screening.

In terms of moored sediment traps and water column time series, AtlantECO is expected to sequence 18S and 16S rDNA from samples collected with long-term sediment traps deployed at 196 m depth at the LTER HAUSGARTEN central station in Fram Strait during three recent annual cycles (2016/17 - 2017/18 - 2018/19 - 2019/21). The technician hired by funds of AtlantECO accomplished the processing of sediment trap samples for molecular microbial biodiversity studies. This procedure entailed the time-consuming picking of swimmers from the samples, wet splitting to generate subsamples, filtration of subsamples, and isolation of genomic DNA. In a pilot study, a first batch of 18 samples collected in the period July 2016 – July 2017 was subjected to sequencing of the 18S and the 16S gene. Sequencing of the 16S gene was successful for all samples, with ~100 k – 200 k high-quality reads obtained per sample. Sequencing of the 18S was only successful for 11 samples, while the number of high-quality reads per sample varied from ~ 30 k to 300 k. Sequencing of the remaining legacy samples for 2017-2018 and 2019 -2021 and sequencing of meta-genomes by Genoscope are pending. Preliminary results illustrate the seasonality of marine microbes collected with the sediment traps.

Regarding the All Atlantic flagship cruises, several successful activities were accomplished, including the Mission Microbiomes expedition on board SV Tara. The expedition comprised several topical studies, including

the Amazon River Plume, Vitória-Trindade Seamounts, Coccolithophore Bloom, Weddell Sea & Iceberg, Mesoscale/submesoscale, Benguela Upwelling, African River Plumes, and Senegal Upwelling. Samples for molecular analyses from these studies are being processed and sequenced by CEA / Genoscope. Extensive imaging data and ancillary oceanographic datasets were collected and are under analysis by AtlantECO partners, particularly USP/Brazil and LOV/France.

Two cruises occurred onboard RV Alpha Crucis in 2022 and 2023, covering an important region of the South Atlantic. Samples from these cruises will be subject to DNA sequencing by UFSCar.

The Southern Ocean Seasonal Experiment (SCALE) winter cruise 2022 on board SA Agulhas II collected samples for microbial community analysis in the Southern Ocean. The samples are currently undergoing analysis, including amplicon sequencing.

AMT cruises on board RSS Discovery are multidisciplinary surveys of biology, chemistry, and physics oceanographic research, covering various regions of the Atlantic Ocean. Samples collected during these cruises are undergoing analysis, including amplicon and metaG analyses.

The All Atlantic Ocean Microbiome Sampling Day is held annually. The second edition was carried out in September 2023, with the incorporation of four laboratories from Colombia. Samples collected during this event are currently undergoing analysis at UFSCar.

The all Atlantic Sail-4-Science aims to develop and implement a simplified version of AtlantECO's protocols for citizen scientists. It involves the development and testing of affordable plankton sampling, genomics, and imaging kits for citizen science. These kits were tested during sailings on three different citizen boats between November 2022 and August 2023, involving participants with various backgrounds. Feedback was collected to improve the instruments, protocols, and understand the challenges of obtaining high-quality data in a citizen science context.

Continuous Plankton Recorders (CPR) surveys were carried out to collect phyto- and zooplankton samples between Brazil and South Africa. Despite facing operational challenges, six tows have been completed to date, with samples collected from various sections of the route. These samples are being analyzed for phytoplankton and zooplankton composition, revealing different taxonomic groups and variations in abundances along the route, particularly with higher abundances near the Walvis Ridge section. The survey has also detected microplastic fibers, with the highest concentration found near the Brazilian coast.

The subtask Genomics, Carbon and Plastic analysis of Moored Sediment Trap samples focuses on analyzing moored sediment trap samples from three Atlantic locations: Porcupine Abyssal Plain (PAP), Northern Oligotrophic Gyre (NOG), and Southern Oligotrophic Gyre (SOG). The analysis includes particulate organic carbon (POC) and microplastic assessments. POC analysis for PAP samples is complete, while NOG and SOG samples are being prepared. Microplastics are being extracted and identified from these samples, with various synthetic polymer types detected, along with additives and plasticizers. Flux calculations for microplastics and mass fluxes are also planned based on the collected data.

Collaborations with third-party sampling programs have been performed and are scheduled for the near future on various research vessels and monitoring platforms. These collaborations have resulted in valuable data related to Amazon plume studies, coccolithophore bloom studies, Southern Ocean studies, Benguela ecosystem studies, Senegal upwelling studies, and assessments of Brazilian coastal ecosystems and the Gulf of Mexico. Continuous observations, including hydrography, nutrient levels, phytoplankton communities, and zooplankton abundance, have been made during these expeditions, contributing to a deeper understanding of the dynamics of these ecosystems. The collected data will further enrich the AtlantECO project's research efforts.

2 Introduction

The AtlantECO Project aims to study the Atlantic Ocean from pole to pole to determine the structure and function of the Atlantic microbiome in the context of ocean circulation and presence of pollutants to assess 1) its role in driving the dynamics of Atlantic ecosystems at basin and regional scales; 2) its potential of being used as a sensor of ecosystem state and 3) the mechanism by which it drives the provision of ecosystem services.

In order to deliver this, the project builds on four activity streams (AS)

- **AS1: Assess the status of the ecosystem structures, functions, health and services** at regional, basin and all Atlantic scales and provide high quality gridded data products and maps
- **AS2: Enhance knowledge and innovate** by adopting standard optical and genetic observations protocols, cutting-edge network analysis methods and better parametrisation of connectivity and biogeochemical models
- **AS3: Assess drivers and stressors of change and forecast** their impact on tipping points and recovery of ecosystem structures, functions and services and develop eco-socio-economic models to predict their future states
- **AS4: Share and use** capacity and knowledge across the four continents bordering the Atlantic Ocean ensuring a seamless engagement between science, industry, policy and society.

AtlantECO addresses three major challenges **microbiome, plastics and the plastisphere** and **seascape and connectivity** and defines these as the scientific concepts underpinning the Project which, together with their interactions, will help address the gap in current knowledge and understanding on how they affect ecology, biodiversity, sensitivity to climate change and the potential for a sustainable exploitation of Atlantic natural resources. Building on the knowledge acquired about the status and dynamics of the Atlantic ecosystem, an additional challenge will be to optimize a set of tools and metrics to tightly couple ecosystem functioning and socio-economic activities, integrating them in a unified framework with Eco-Socio-Economic analyses and projections, which we consider a prerequisite for the sustainable management of the Atlantic Ocean. A final challenge to be addressed by AtlantECO is the design of a strategy and of procedures to guarantee that the new unified framework will be implemented in a systemic way so that all the components of the implicated societies in countries bordering the basin will contribute to the implementation and will fully benefit from it.

AtlantECO focuses on five ecosystem services:

- **ES1:** Climate support system: carbon drawdown and storage
- **ES2:** Deep ocean life support system: transfer of matter & energy to mesopelagic and seabed ecosystems.
- **ES3:** Food security and the trophic fluxes: fisheries and aquaculture.
- **ES4:** Healthy planet, healthy people: biohazards, cycling of plastics and pollutants
- **ES5:** Biodiversity: resilience, adaptation and contribution to the Bioeconomy, including new chemicals

One objective of WP4 is to generate new observations about microbiomes, plastics and the plastisphere. It is implemented by Task 4.2 through dedicated sampling activities in the North and South Atlantic (see details below), and its results are exploited in first instance by WPs 2, 5 and 6, and shared with the wider research community following the project's Data Management Plan (WP10). Progress was achieved by the six Subtasks implementing this objective, as reported below. This deliverable is the final version of a series of reports on AtlantECO's augmented observations resulting from Task 4.3.

3 Molecular (DNA/RNA) analysis of legacy samples

AMT samples/ metabarcode sequencing

The Atlantic Meridional Transect (AMT) programme, established in 1995 and coordinated by Plymouth Marine Laboratory, has completed 30 research cruises between the UK and the South Atlantic. These cruises span more than 100° of latitude and reach depths of up to 1000 m, allowing detailed investigation of the structure and biogeochemistry of planktonic ecosystems across environments ranging from subpolar to tropical, and from nutrient rich upwelling regions to oligotrophic gyres. Since 2009, hundreds of samples for molecular analysis have been collected, most of which are stored at PML. From these, 250 samples were selected by the AtlantECO programme for 16S (V4V5; 515F-Y and 926R) and 18S rRNA (V4; 528iF and 964iR) gene metabarcode sequencing, focusing on broad geographic coverage and regions that are underrepresented in current sequence databases. To enable spatial and temporal comparisons, sampling emphasised surface waters, although Deep Chlorophyll Maximum (DCM) samples from AMT27 were also included to help PML scientists link microbial community composition with nitrification rates at depth. A summary of samples selected (cruise, date, latitudes covered, depths and numbers of samples sequenced) are shown below.

Sequence data was initially processed by EBI using MGnify (available through the AtlantECO Data Hub). PML has further refined the analyses of the 18S rRNA gene sequence data to improve annotation accuracy and coverage (see below).

Analyses of the eukaryote (18S) sequence data set showed clear differences in species richness across the Atlantic transect. Alpha diversity metrics indicated that samples collected in Longhurst ecological provinces near the equator exhibited the highest within sample richness, whereas those from the Northeast Atlantic Shelf, the Subantarctic water ring and Antarctic displayed notably lower richness (Figure 4.1A). Principal Coordinates Analysis (PCoA) further revealed a strong separation of samples by geographical province. When environmental variables were overlaid onto the ordination, the patterns suggested that temperature play an important role in structuring the eukaryotic plankton communities across the transect (Figure 4.1B).

Figure 4.1: Diversity assesment of eukaryotic community composition (A) observed 18S ASV richness across samples grouped by Longhurst provinces. Boxes represent the interquartile range, the horizontal line indicates the median, and whiskers extend to 1.5x the interquartile range. Individual points represent sample-level richness values. (B) Principal Coordinates Analysis (PCoA) based on Aitchison's distance (Euclidean distance of CLR-transformed ASV abundances). Points are coloured according to *in situ* temperature and shaped by Longhurst province.

The 16S sequence data showed the dominant prokaryote groups present were grouped into Longhurstian provinces, highlighting clear geographic differences in prokaryote community composition (Figure 4.2). For example, NE Atlantic Shelf communities contain higher proportions of ammonia and nitrite oxidising taxa (Thaumarchaeota and Nitrospinae). Subantartic and Anartartic communities contained higher abundance of Oceanospirillales, heterotrophs often linked with organic-rich environments and algal metabolites alongside the nitrogen fixing Nostocales. Overall, four broad community patterns were identified, three of which were strongly linked to variations in temperature and nutrients.

Figure 4.2: Geographical Differences to Prokaryote Community Composition (A) Shows the average relative sequence abundance of the main archaeal and bacterial taxa found in surface samples from each Longhurst ecological province. A type 3 SIMPROF test was used to group taxa with similar spatial patterns into clusters (SPF group). Three of these clusters showed strong geographic differences in where they occurred. (B) Spearman correlations reveal that temperature and nutrient changes across the transect were major factors influencing the relative sequence abundance of three clusters. Blue indicates a positive correlation, red a negative correlation and grey no correlation (n = 249).

In all cases, samples were filtered through 0.22 µm Sterivex filters, preserved by adding 1 mL RNA later Solution and stored at -70 °C until further analyses. Details can be found in the report for each cruise (available from <https://www.amt-uk.org/cruises>). One DCM sample was selected from the -70 °C freezer in error.

Bioinformatic Analyses

Genoscope have provided 16S and 18S rRNA gene data for samples collected from six cruises. These data were processed by EBI using the MGnify pipeline (available via AtlantECO project hub, study ID PRJEB78868). In addition, PML independently processed the 18S rRNA gene data (https://github.com/pmlbioinformatics/nda_atlanteco_18s) as follows:

- Demultiplexed sequences were re-oriented and quality trimmed and filtered using *cutadapt*. Amplicon sequence variants (ASVs) were inferred using *DADA2* to correct sequence errors and remove chimeras.
- Contaminant sequences identified in PCR and sequencing controls were assessed using *decontam*.

- To improve annotation accuracy and coverage, PML applied a bespoke taxonomic annotation pipeline that integrates information from multiple reference databases (SILVA, PR2, MetaZooGene and NCBI), reconciles conflicting *BLAST* assignments, and standardises taxonomic identifiers using *obistools*. This annotation pipeline is currently being refined, with the aim of making open access when publishing our main findings from our data analyses.
- Annotated ASV sequences were curated to remove off-target taxa (Bacteria, Viruses and Archaea) and ASVs with insufficient representation were removed based on representation within samples (≥ 0.005 % relative abundance) and prevalence across samples (> 2 samples). The retained ASVs accounted for 95.1 % of the total read depth, retaining the majority of sequencing effort within a concentrated set of consistently detected taxa.

Exploitable Results

- Open source 18S sequence data (GenBank and OBIS) with metadata (to include CTD, nutrients)
- Open source 16S sequences data (GenBank and OBIS) with metadata (to include CTD, nutrients)
- Open source metatranscriptomic data (AMT27; October 2017)
- Open source repository containing scripts to process and analyse 18S sequence dataset (github link as above)
- A manuscript describing eukaryote community composition across the transect
- A manuscript describing prokaryote community composition and activity across the transect, focusing on nitrogen cycling processes.

Table 4.1. Summary of samples sequenced.

leg	cruise	dates	highest latitude	lowest latitude	depths		
						18S	16S
AMT21	D371	Oct. 2011	29.1188	-21.0955	surface	10	10
AMT23	JR300	Oct. 2013	45.002	-43.7087	40 surface; 1 DCM*	41	41
AMT24	JR303	Oct. 2014	47.572	-45.2875	surface	29	29
AMT27	DY084	Oct. 2017	47.2689	-53.5507	56 surface; 35 DCM	82	91
AMT28	JR18001	Oct. 2018	48.469	-48.199	surface	54	54
AMT29	DY110	Oct/Nov. 2019	49.04818	-34.7771	surface	41	42

Plastisphere

Sequencing of Plastisphere legacy datasets is complete and workflow strategies (Figures 4.3 and 4.4) and dataset output (Figures 4.5 and 4.6) are summarized below. All Genoscope-sequenced metagenomes (MG) have been deposited in EBI and are available via the AtlantECO Data Hub. These datasets are private at the moment but are being processed and analyzed as part of a PhD thesis funded by the Advanced ERC ViBRANT-SEA grant awarded to PI Amaral-Zettler. A paper is in preparation by PhD student Or Amar who has presented these results at the AtlantECO GA meetings in Vigo and the Azores and most recently at the Cell Symposium in Amsterdam. Figure 4.3 summarizes a generalized workflow for amplicon and MG library construction. Fungal sequencing was suspended due to technical issues related to primer usage and design.

AtlantECO Molecular Workflow

Figure 4.3. Workflow for Plastisphere Amplicon and MG library processing.

Metagenomic analysis pipeline

Figure 4.4. Pipeline for analyses of MG libraries.

To date, 359 AtlantECO amplicons have been created and sequenced with the 3-domain primers. Of these 359 samples, 335 have been further sequenced with Eukaryotic-specific primers. The amplicon data is being prepared for submission to EBI and will be deposited by the end of the project period.

3-DOMAIN Amplicons

Eukaryotic Amplicons

Figure 4.5. Plastic collected samples across Longhurst Zones for Three Domain and Eukaryotic-specific amplicons.

We presently have 81 Metagenomes sequenced, 52 to a depth of 250 million reads and 29 to a depth of 50 million reads. Assemblies and binning have been performed in collaboration with Shinichi Sunagawa's group at ETH. A total of 5,295 MAGs were assembled. PhD candidate Amar will work with MSc students and NIOZ data managers to analyze the amplicon datasets. 31 of the 81 MG datasets also have associated amplicon data.

Figure 4.6. Distribution of Metagenomic Datasets.

4 AtlantECO's Augmented Observations

The objective of Task 4.2 is to generate new observations about microbiomes, plastics and the plastisphere. It was implemented during the second reporting period by partners EMBL, USP, EMBRC-ERIC, EMSO-ERIC, CEA, AWI, CNRS, CSIR, FTO, FURG, NIOZ, NOC, MBA, SU, SZN, UCT, UFSC, UFSCar, UniLIV and UP through seven activities:

- Analysis of legacy samples (Subtask 4.2.0)
- Flagship cruises (Subtask 4.2.1)
- All-Atlantic Ocean Sampling Day (Subtask 4.2.2)
- All-Atlantic Sail-4-Science (Subtask 4.2.3)
- Continuous Plankton Recorder (Subtask 4.2.4)
- Genomics, Carbon and Plastic analysis of Moored Sediment Trap samples (Subtask 4.2.5)
- Third party cruises (Subtask 4.2.6)

The sampling effort of AtlantECO's augmented observation activities totals 3,125 person*days (Figure 4.1), which were deployed during flagship cruises (77%), third party cruises (11%), All-Atlantic OSD and Sail4Science (7%) and the Continuous Plankton Recorder survey (2.4%).

Figure 4.1 Sampling effort deployed during AtlantECO's augmented observation activities (total 3,125 person*days), including flagship cruises (shades of blue; 77%), third party cruises (shades of green; 11%), All-Atlantic OSD and Sail4Science (shades of orange; 7%) and the Continuous Plankton Recorder survey (shades of red; 2.4%).

Task 4.2 gathered over 21,000 new samples, the majority of which targets the analysis of prokaryotes (23%) and small eukaryotes (41%), but also include samples targeting viruses (13%), larger eukaryotic plankton (8%), and biogeochemistry (14%) (Figure 4.2 A). In accordance with AtlantECO's objective to fill a knowledge gap in the southern hemisphere, the vast majority of samples gathered by Task 4.2 were collected in the tropics (46%) and in sub-tropical, temperate and polar zones of the South Atlantic (45%) (Figure 4.2 A).

Roughly 9,000 samples, i.e. 43% of all samples gathered by Task 4.2 were analysed (Figure 4.2 B); The other 12,000 samples will be biobanked and analysed pending co-funding from future projects. Out of the 9,000 samples, 37% are analysed for genomics (Figure 4.2 C) and 46% are analysed for phenomics (Figure 4.2 D), including flow cytometry, HPLC, microscopy, flowcam, planktoscope and zooscan.

All types of activity have successfully contributed to Task 4.2. Not surprisingly, the majority of samples gathered by Task 4.2 were collected as part of AtlantECO's flagship expeditions on board three research sailing boats and three oceanographic research vessels (Figure 4.3 A), in particular by the eleven topical studies of Mission Microbiomes on board *SU Tara*. The analysis of the samples progressed surprisingly well across the different types of activities (Figure 4.3 B) and topical studies (Figure 4.3 C), with a marked lag during the second period for the last flagship cruises in Brazil on board the *Veleiro ECO/Pangeia* and the *Alpha Crucis*. A redistribution of the budget in the third amendment of the project's GA provided additional funds to conduct analyses in Brazil during the third period.

The contribution of the different types of activities to the collection of samples for genomic protocols is dominated by AtlantECO's flagship cruises (55%), the legacy sample analysis (25%), and third party cruises (16%) (Figure 4.4 A), whereas that of samples for phenomics protocols is dominated by AtlantECO's flagship cruises (78%), the Continuous Plankton Recorder survey (15%), and the All-Atlantic Sail-4-Science (7%) (Figure 4.5 A).

Partners EMBL, FURG, MBA, NOC, CNRS, EMSO-PLOCAN, AWI, NIOZ and PML presented preliminary results of the Continuous Plankton Recorder survey (Subtask 4.2.4), the flagship Mission Microbiomes (Subtask 4.2.1), the analysis of sediment trap carbon and microplastics (Subtask 4.2.5) and the analysis of legacy samples (Subtask 4.2.0) during AtlantECO's scientific meetings in Vigo (September 2024) and in Ponta Delgado (September 2025).

A.		target entities & size-fractions												
zones & latitudes	All protocols (# samples)	dissolved elements	0.02 µm	viruses	0.2 µm	bacteria & archaea	2 µm	unicellular eukaryotes	20 µm	mixed eukaryotes	200 µm	multicellular eukaryotes	2000 µm	TOTAL
	90°N													
	polar	0		0		59		73		66		51		1%
	66°N													
	temperate	0		6		192		258		292		2		4%
	35°N													
	sub-tropical	0		12		164		292		244		2		3%
	23°N													
	tropical	1,443		1,429		2,329		2,656		1,413		582		46%
	23°S													
	sub-tropical	626		460		767		838		504		683		18%
	35°S													
	temperate	793		798		1,110		1,211		561		389		23%
66°S														
polar	172		151		203		282		102		31		4%	
90°S														
TOTAL		14%		13%		23%		26%		15%		8%	21,246	

B.		target entities & size-fractions												
zones & latitudes	All protocols (# samples)	dissolved elements	0.02 µm	viruses	0.2 µm	bacteria & archaea	2 µm	unicellular eukaryotes	20 µm	mixed eukaryotes	200 µm	multicellular eukaryotes	2000 µm	TOTAL
	90°N													
	polar	0		0		59		73		59		51		3%
	66°N													
	temperate	0		6		133		185		206		0		6%
	35°N													
	sub-tropical	0		12		101		222		149		0		5%
	23°N													
	tropical	414		530		945		1,274		720		56		44%
	23°S													
	sub-tropical	170		142		271		358		251		354		17%
	35°S													
	temperate	257		242		401		672		284		103		22%
66°S														
polar	22		43		47		199		37		2		4%	
90°S														
TOTAL		10%		11%		22%		33%		19%		6%	9,050	

Figure 4.2 Number of samples collected by all activities of AtlantECO’s augmented observations, distributed among the different target entities & size-fractions (columns) and the different latitudinal zones in the Atlantic Ocean (rows).

- (A) Total number of samples from all protocols, including chemistry, genomics, proteomics, metabolomics and phenomics;
- (B) same as (A) but only samples that were analysed during the second and third periods;

C.		target entities & size-fractions												
		Genomics protocols (# samples)	dissolved elements	0.02 µm	viruses	0.2 µm	bacteria & archaea	2 µm	unicellular eukaryotes	20 µm	mixed eukaryotes	200 µm	multicellular eukaryotes	2000 µm
zones & latitudes	90°N													
	polar	0		0		59		73		59		51		7%
	66°N													
	temperate	0		6		133		185		133		0		14%
	35°N													
	sub-tropical	0		12		101		222		121		0		14%
	23°N													
	tropical	0		35		207		536		230		23		31%
	23°S													
	sub-tropical	0		16		81		168		90		14		11%
	35°S													
	temperate	0		38		102		373		56		25		18%
	66°S													
polar	0		0		0		152		0		2		5%	
90°S														
TOTAL				3%		21%		52%		21%		3%		3,303

D.		target entities & size-fractions												
		Phenomics protocols (# samples)	dissolved elements	0.02 µm	viruses	0.2 µm	bacteria & archaea	2 µm	unicellular eukaryotes	20 µm	mixed eukaryotes	200 µm	multicellular eukaryotes	2000 µm
zones & latitudes	90°N													
	polar	0		0		0		0		0		0		0%
	66°N													
	temperate	0		0		0		0		73		0		2%
	35°N													
	sub-tropical	0		0		0		0		28		0		1%
	23°N													
	tropical	0		267		613		613		457		0		47%
	23°S													
	sub-tropical	0		63		190		190		161		340		23%
	35°S													
	temperate	0		136		299		299		228		78		25%
	66°S													
polar	0		22		47		47		37		0		4%	
90°S														
TOTAL				12%		27%		27%		23%		10%		4,188

Figure 4.2 Number of samples collected by all activities of AtlantECO’s augmented observations, distributed among the different target entities & size-fractions (columns) and the different latitudinal zones in the Atlantic Ocean (rows).

(C) same as (B) but only for genomics protocols;

(D) same as (B) but only for phenomics protocols, including flow cytometry, HPLC, microscopy, flowcam and zooscan.

Figure 4.3 Progress of analyses for samples collected using all protocols, including biogeochemistry, genomics, proteomics, metabolomics and phenomics. In (B) and (C), numbers are split between analyses that were carried out during the second period (green), those carried out during the third period (yellow) and those pending co-funding (blue).

- (A) total number of samples per type of activity;
- (B) number of samples per augmented observation activity; and
- (C) number of samples per topical study of Mission Microbiomes.

C. all protocols - by Mission Microbiomes

Figure 4.3 Progress of analyses for samples collected using all protocols, including biogeochemistry, genomics, proteomics, metabolomics and phenomics. In (B) and (C), numbers are split between analyses that were carried out during the second period (green), those carried out during the third period (yellow) and those pending co-funding (blue).

- (A) total number of samples per type of activity;
- (B) number of samples per augmented observation activity; and
- (C) number of samples per topical study of Mission Microbiomes.

Figure 4.4 Progress of analyses for samples collected using genomics protocols only. In (B) and (C), numbers are split between analyses that were carried out during the second period (green), those carried out during the third period (yellow) and those pending co-funding (blue).

- (A) total number of samples per type of activity;
- (B) number of samples per augmented observation activity; and
- (C) number of samples per topical study of Mission Microbiomes.

C. genomics protocols - by Mission Microbiomes

Figure 4.4 Progress of analyses for samples collected using genomics protocols only. In (B) and (C), numbers are split between analyses that were carried out during the second period (green), those carried out during the third period (yellow) and those pending co-funding (blue).

- (A) total number of samples per type of activity;
- (B) number of samples per augmented observation activity; and
- (C) number of samples per topical study of Mission Microbiomes.

Figure 4.7 Progress of analyses for samples collected using phenomics protocols only, including flow cytometry, HPLC, microscopy, flowcam, planktoscope and zooscan. In (B) and (C), numbers are split between analyses that were carried out during the second period (green), those carried out during the third period (yellow) and those pending co-funding (blue).

- (A) total number of samples per type of activity;
- (B) number of samples per augmented observation activity; and
- (C) number of samples per topical study of Mission Microbiomes.

C. phenomics protocols - by Mission Microbiomes

Figure 4.7 Progress of analyses for samples collected using phenomics protocols only, including flow cytometry, HPLC, microscopy, flowcam, planktoscope and zooscan. In (B) and (C), numbers are split between analyses that were carried out during the second period (green), those carried out during the third period (yellow) and those pending co-funding (blue).

- (A) total number of samples per type of activity;
- (B) number of samples per augmented observation activity; and
- (C) number of samples per topical study of Mission Microbiomes.

5 The all Atlantic flagship cruises (lead: USP)

The AtlantECO project had as its central objective the understanding of how physical, biogeochemical, and ecological processes structure marine microbiomes across the Atlantic Ocean, integrating multiple spatial scales, from basin-wide to submesoscale, and different environmental compartments (surface ocean, deep ocean, and atmosphere).

Flagship SV Tara - Mission Microbiomes AtlantECO

Between December 2020 and late 2022, the French schooner Tara operated as a dedicated oceanographic platform for Mission Microbiomes, one of the flagship expeditions of the AtlantECO programme. The mission involved coordinated sampling across the South Atlantic Ocean along the coasts of South America and West Africa and reaching Antarctic waters, encompassing dozens of port calls and hydrographic stations.

Scientific objectives centred on characterizing the structure and functioning of marine microbiomes, including viruses, bacteria, protists, and zooplankton, and understanding their ecological roles in carbon cycling, climate regulation, and responses to environmental pressures such as plastic pollution and warming. Standardized protocols were applied for *in situ* collection of water and associated microbiome samples from surface and deeper layers, alongside measurements of physical and biogeochemical parameters to link microbial diversity with environmental gradients.

Data generated during the cruises have contributed to high-resolution genetic, imaging, and environmental datasets that support improved models of microbial biogeography and ecosystem dynamics across key Atlantic regions, in alignment with AtlantECO's integrated observational framework.

The expedition comprised the following topical studies:

- Topical Study “Sigrid Neumann Leitão” - Amazon River Plume
- Topical Study “Tagea Bjonberg” - Vitória-Trindade Seamounts
- Topical Study “Ana Maria Gayoso” - Coccolithophore Bloom
- Topical Study “Maria Klenova” - Weddell Sea & Iceberg
- Topical Study “Emmy Noether” - Mesoscale/submesoscale
- Topical Study “Lesley Shackleton” - Benguela Upwelling
- Topical Study “Naledi Pandor” - African River Plumes
- Topical Study - Senegal Upwelling

Topical Study “Sigrid Neumann Leitão” - Amazon River Plume

The Amazon plume and its interaction with the North Brazilian Current was studied from August to October 2021, including port calls in Fort-de-France, Macapa, Belem and Salvador de Bahia. Chief scientists were Stéphane Pesant (EMBL) and Paula Huber (UFSCar). While rivers are an important source of pollutants from land into the ocean, their plumes also transport large amounts of nutrients that fuel primary production in the coastal waters and open ocean, especially in oligotrophic basins. On the western side of the South Atlantic the two main river inputs are from the Amazon River and the Rio de la Plata, whose plumes are regulated by the local western boundary currents. One objective of this campaign was to characterise the river input to the ocean and subsequent dilution processes, and to study changes in the diversity of marine microbiomes across those gradients. An important objective of this first campaign in the Atlantic was also to test new sampling strategies, equipment, and protocols.

The campaign was conducted aboard Tara in international waters and the Exclusive Economic Zones of French Guiana and Brazil. The sampling area is characterized by the Amazon River plume and anticyclonic eddies from

the North Brazilian Current. Sampling involved various locations, including the Amazon plume, cyclonic and anticyclonic eddies, and the Amazon River itself. AtlantECO protocols were carried out at all stations for omics, imaging, and biogeochemistry analysis. Protocols were also in place to collect Sargassum.

Omics samples collected at 11 stations (encompassing various depths and plankton size fractions), are undergoing processing for amplicon, metaG, and metaT analyses at UFSCar.

Topical Study “Tagea Bjonberg” - Vitória-Trindade Seamounts

Biodiversity hotspots around Trinidad Seamounts were studied in October 2021 followed by an important port call in Rio de Janeiro. The chief scientist was Samuel Chaffron (CNRS). The main objective of this campaign was to enable the potential discovery of new bioproducts & chemicals for industrial applications with high socio-economic value, such as new ways to produce pharmaceutical products or natural enzymes able to digest complex molecules such as pollutants or plastics. Given the bioprospecting focus of this leg, sampling stations were all located within international waters, along the Vitória-Trindade Chain (VTC) consisting of 11 heterogeneous seamounts. The sampling area will also be studied by the H2020 Atlantic project iAtlantic (Integrated Assessment of Atlantic Marine Ecosystems in Space and Time), so this campaign will hopefully lead to synergies and collaborations between AtlantECO and iAtlantic.

Topical Study “Monica Montu” - Southern Brazilian Shelf

The Southern Brazilian Shelf is the most productive fishing ground of the 8000 km Brazilian Shelf due to the northern spread of La Plata Plume and the Santa Marta Cape upwelling, both driven by the interaction of seasonal winds and western boundary currents. The topical study was developed upon request of the Brazilian team being a successful bottom-up research topic. It was conducted after an important Port-Call in Itajaí (Santa Catarina) co-hosted by SV Tara and SV Veleiro ECO. The objective of this campaign was to link ecosystem function to the microbiome biodiversity, in the upwelling, open ocean and under the southern estuarine plumes input (three oceanographic stations). An important objective of this first campaign was to boost capacity building of Brazilian early career researchers; AtlantECO post doc Andrea Green Koettker (UFSC) was its Chief Scientist. AtlantECO protocols were carried out at the stations for omics, imaging, and biogeochemistry analysis. The first IFCB (Imaging FlowCytobot) transect was conducted in the Southwestern Atlantic. UFSC analyses mesozooplankton and microplankton processed in different image systems (FlowCam, ZooScan, IFCB) including the validation in EcoTaxa. UFSCar provides omics analysis.

Topical Study “Ana Maria Gayoso” - Coccolithophore Bloom

Dynamics of a coccolithophore bloom on/off the Patagonian shelf were studied in December 2021, including port calls in Buenos Aires and Ushuaia. The chairs of the topical study were Flora Vincent (then Weizmann, now EMBL) and Federico Ibarbalz (CONICET). Flora Vincent was also chief scientist onboard Tara. Every spring, the Patagonian shelf experiences massive phytoplankton blooms. While diatoms and dinoflagellates dominate at the beginning, gigantic patches of high reflectance waters associated with coccolithophores can be detected towards December. These develop in long (100-1000 km) south-to-north streaks along the shelf-break for several weeks and are advected northwards due to the effect of the strong Malvinas Current. Whether the bloom is only advected or also benefits from upwellings and therefore from fertilisation processes triggered by the current along the shelf-break is currently not known. The main objective was to study the ecosystem dynamics of a coccolithophore bloom and demise. Particularly for the cruise in December onboard Tara, a team on land analysed satellite products to select candidate blooming spots for *in situ* confirmation via inline and flow cytometry optical determinations. Once the identity and magnitude of the bloom were confirmed, a set of three drifters with GPS were released in order to sample a consistent water mass for several days in a row.

For the sampling onboard Tara, the group of Assaf Vardi (Weizmann Institute) has already obtained flow cytometry abundances for viral, bacterial and coccolithophore populations along the cruise, as well as

metabolic markers that indicate viral infection of the coccolithophore *Emiliana huxleyi*. Some contextual data has been generated by Guillaume Bourdin (University of Maine), namely satellite products and continuous inline measurements. They have been partially explored by Federico Ibarbalz and Martin Saraceno in Argentina. For details on the complementary November cruise onboard Housay, see Third Party sections below.

Topical Study “Maria Klenova” - Weddell Sea & Iceberg

The Weddell Sea and the sub-mesoscale dynamics surrounding icebergs were studied in January and February 2022. The chief scientist was Alessandro Tagliabue (UniLIV). The main objective of the Tara Antarctic leg was two-fold: (1) to sample across well-established physical and biogeochemical gradients; and (2) to conduct a multi-day process study around an iceberg. Both are concerned with capturing the response of the microbiome to variability in the seascape introduced by topography, frontal systems and freshwater (both melting sea ice, glaciers and icebergs). These scientific objectives are motivated by the urgent need to understand how the microbiome of the Antarctic seas will respond to climate change, as well as to generate baseline understanding in this under-sampled region.

Topical Study “Emmy Noether” - Mesoscale/submesoscale

Mesoscale eddies and sub-mesoscale filaments were studied in March-April 2022 from Punta Arenas to Cape Town. The chief scientist was Rémi Laxenaire (CNES/CNRS). The two objectives of this leg were (1) to study a subsurface-intensified cyclonic eddy lying between the Subantarctic and Polar fronts of the Antarctic Circumpolar Current, and (2) to study the frontal zone between the South Atlantic and the Southern Ocean marked by an anticyclonic eddy and a meander. The two eddies located at approximately 48.5°S, 25°W and 38°S, 6°E were dissected using a combination of high resolution underway sampling and in depth sampling of the epi- and mesopelagic layers.

Topical Study “Lesley Shackleton” - Benguela Upwelling

The Benguela upwelling system was studied in May 2022, including important port calls in Cape Town and Walvis Bay. The chief scientist was Emma Rocke (UCT). The Benguela upwelling is one of four major Eastern Boundary upwelling systems (EBUS) in the world. Coastal upwelling is a major oceanic process driven by prominent currents, of which those within Eastern Boundary Upwelling Systems are most important globally. These systems are present along the western shores of landmasses in the Pacific and Atlantic Oceans where they comprise vast regions of coastal ocean water. High productivity brings with it low to no oxygen zones which endanger the local ecosystem services. While macrofauna either die or move away, the microbiome in these areas remain active. We were interested in sampling different stages of upwelling in the Benguela upwelling region to understand the evolution of the microbiome before, during and after an upwelling event and in these low oxygen minimum zones. Four stations along the St Helena Bay Monitoring line, a transect which has been sampled seasonally for the past 25 years, were sampled using the suite of protocols used throughout Mission Microbiomes, thus extending the range of measurements routinely done by UCT along that monitoring line. The South African sampling effort was complemented with seasonal samples taken from The RV Algoa in collaboration with the South African Department of Forestry, Fisheries and the environment (DFFE). It is important to note that the Northern Benguela (North of Luderitz) and the Southern Benguela (South of Luderitz) are defined as two different systems. The primary difference between the two relates to the seasonal (austral summer) upwelling only in the South, influenced by Antarctic and Agulhas water masses, versus year round SE winds and upwelling in the north, with a more tropical Angola current influence. Our sampling efforts allowed for an in depth comparison of the microbiomes of these two systems for the first time.

We have analysed almost all underway and satellite data in order to contextualise the environment from when our samples were taken. Analysis of the flowcam data and biogeochemical rates is underway. Next steps include sequencing the 0.2-2µm size fraction metagenome from all stations.

Topical Study “Naledi Pandor” - African River Plumes

The scope of the topical study was to sample the plumes of four African rivers: the Orange river (Namibia), Congo river (Angola & Congo), Gambia river (Gambia) and Casamance river (Senegal). The scientific objectives were (1) to describe changes in microbial life along the river-plume-ocean continuum, (2) to evaluate plastic pollution associated with the river and the diversity of its plastisphere, and (3) in the case of the Orange River, to investigate the effects of aerial transport from the Namib desert on marine productivity and associated microbiomes.

Topical Study - Senegal Upwelling

The two principal objectives of this TS were 1) to characterize the “pre-upwelling” marine microbiome state, and 2) to characterize the Oxygen Minimum zone (OMZ), off the coast of Gambia and Senegal. The samplings during this leg were established in collaboration with the IRD (Dr. Eric Machu) who are regularly sampling this area at specific stations. Considering the IRD cruise during the next upwelling season, which took place in December 2022, we coordinated the sampling to capture the state of plankton ecosystems during the pre-upwelling season, in August 2022. This is of particular interest as upwelling systems are usually sampled during winter (upwelling season). Characterizing highly resolved plankton community structures through omics between summer and winter seasons will also help us to better understand the transition mechanisms of the marine microbiomes in this large upwelling system. In addition, characterizing the OMZ in this system will allow us to evaluate its seasonal evolution and its impact on highly productive marine plankton communities sustaining the very productive fisheries in the zone.

Flagship SV Veleiro ECO & Pangeia - Brazilian Rivers and Estuaries

Brazilian partners organised several port call events in Brazil, including two joint events with both SV Tara and SV Veleiro ECO in Rio de Janeiro and Itajai in November 2021. These events inspired successful Port Calls organized by UFSC in 2023 covering the largest soybean export port (Paranagua, Parana) on board SV Veleiro ECO, the largest metropolitan area of the northeastern coast (Recife), and a touristic hot spot in the eastern coast (Porto Seguro, Bahia), on board SV Pangeia (Figure 5.1).

(Figure 5.1). Research and Ocean Literacy merge in the Port Calls throughout the Brazilian coast co-hosted by SU Tara, SU Veleiro Eco and SU Pangeia in 2021 and 2023.

UFSC team conducted two research and outreach expeditions in 2023 in three Brazilian rivers and adjacent coastal waters — Itajaí-Açu, São Francisco, and Buranhém — concluding the studies along Brazilian Coast, that started aboard Tara in 2021, in the Amazon Plume expedition (Figure 5.2). Itajaí-Açu River drains an area fully impacted by pesticides, being the second largest port in the country in container traffic. São Francisco River dams across its 3200 km provide 15 % of Brazilian energy but caused changes of the river flow and a general loss of land and water biodiversity. Buranhém River is in the historical site of the Portuguese arrival in Brazil, being closely associated with the coral reefs and an important touristic destination. In these rivers, samples were collected in their estuarine plumes, and in the shallow shelf (Figure 5.3). Overall, the sampling strategy prioritized surface samplings (Z00) during ebb tide conditions, aiming to investigate the influence of rivers on the adjacent coastal zone. The number of stations and protocols conducted on board, as well as the total number of samples collected in each river are presented in Figure 5.2. The Itajaí-Açu River expedition occurred from March 01 to 07, aboard SV Veleiro ECO, when an average of 85 samples were collected per day, including the microbiome, microplastics and biogeochemical parameters. Research in the São Francisco and Buranhém Rivers was carried out aboard SV Pangeia (Figure 5.4), departing from Recife — where a Port Call was held — heading south along the coast of Brazil. In the São Francisco River (at the border of Alagoas and Sergipe state, northeastern Brazilian coast), the research team worked along five days, from November 04 to 08, on three oceanographic stations - River, Plume, and Canyon in the inner Shelf (Figure 5.3), during more than 12 hours nonstop. In each station one hundred (100), 77 and 93 samples were collected, and according to each local depth, including more than one sampling layer. In the Buranhém River, in Porto Seguro (Bahia state), research and Port Call activities took place simultaneously, requiring the team to split their efforts between these two tasks. The researchers on board conducted four research stations from November 15 to 18, including sampling in the sheltered reef area of the Recife de Fora Marine Natural Park (PNMMRF). The expeditions included the previous protocols training at UFSC, a short pilot station moored on shore, and after the arrival, the further storage and/ or delivery of samples to research partners.

Figure 5.2. AtlantECO Expeditions in the Brazilian rivers and their surrounding coastal area.

Figure 5.3 Sampling stations at Itajaí-Açu (#1 and #2 – River Plume; #3 – Ocean; 4 – River; #5 – River mouth), São Francisco (#6 – Plume; #7 – River; #8 – Ocean: São Francisco Canyon) and Buranhem River (#9 – Plume; #10 – Ocean: Reef area; #11 – River mouth, #12 – River).

Figure 5.4 Brazilian rivers and estuaries research on board SU Pangeia - improving women representation in STEM.

UFSC was responsible for analyzing the micro- and mesozooplankton of the samples collected during the 2021 and 2023 expeditions, as well as the 2023 biogeochemical samples. All mesozooplankton samples (F200 protocol) have already been processed in the laboratory, scanned on the ZooScan and uploaded at the EcoTaxa. Samples are in different steps of taxonomic validation related to a PhD thesis. For the three Brazilian rivers, microplankton samples from the F20 protocol, are being imaged on the PlanktoScope. A total of 23 samples were collected across these three rivers: 10 from the Itajaí-Açu River, 8 from Buranhém, and 5 from the São Francisco River. According to the current protocol, updated in collaboration with the Laboratoire d’Oceanographie de Villefranche (LOV), these samples should be imaged in triplicate on the PlanktoScope, followed by particle upload into EcoTaxa for prediction and expert validation. Of the 23 samples collected, 10 have already been imaged and uploaded to EcoTaxa. The remaining samples are in the imaging process and will soon be uploaded to EcoTaxa. The biogeochemical analyses were conducted at UFSC in the Chemical and Biological Oceanography Laboratory, in relation to with the following parameters: Chlorophyll – a, pH, Dissolved Oxygen, Total Suspended Solids (mg/L), Ammonium (NH_4^+), Nitrite + Nitrate ($\text{NO}_2^- + \text{NO}_3^-$), Phosphate (PO_4^{3-}), Silicate (SiO_2). The omics and microplastics samples were sent to Universidade Federal de São Carlos (UFSCar).

Flagship SY Eugen Seibold - North East Atlantic Mission

The research sailing yacht Eugen Seibold is a contamination-free platform operated by the Max Planck Institute for Chemistry (Mainz, Germany) for sampling of the water column and atmosphere for biological, chemical, and physical properties. The 72-foot yacht is designed for sampling of the open ocean for a better understanding of the ocean environment including the overlying atmosphere, air-sea exchange processes at the regional to global scale, and multi-parameter calibration of marine planktic archives and paleo-proxies. Operations in the eastern Northeast Atlantic, from 2019 to 2022, were targeted at a North-to-South transect from subpolar to equatorial waters. From 2023 to 2025, projects focused on the Tropical Eastern Pacific. Figure 5.4 summarizes the cruise tracks and stations. Laboratories for air and seawater analyses are equipped with down-sized and automated state-of-the-art technology. Continuous surface ocean sampling is facilitated by a FerryBox, which provides seawater from the base of the keel at 3.2 m water depth. The atmosphere is sampled about 13 m above the water line. Seawater probes and plankton nets are deployed from the stern of the boat to sample the pelagic ocean.

Microbial communities of the eastern North Atlantic were sampled from surface waters through the keel inlet, and sequentially filtered on 10- μm , 3- μm , and 0.2- μm pore size-filters for DNA analyses. Additional samples were obtained from below the thermocline at 200 m water depth, from the deep chlorophyll maximum (DCM), directly above the DCM, and from the surface mixed layer at 20 m water depth. In parallel, air communities were sampled using a Coriolis- μ air sampler on top of the wheel-house (3.5 m above water line) and filtered at 0.2- μm for DNA analyses. DNA from samples collected at 3 m water depth and the atmosphere were extracted and sequenced on a Illumina MiSeq platform targeting the 16S v4-v5 and 18S v8-v9 regions. Extraction and sequencing of additional samples from water depth profiles of the 3-10 μm fraction are currently being discussed. Quantification of cells is conducted in collaboration with the Max Planck Institute for Marine Microbiology (Bremen, Germany).

Figure 5.4. *S/Y Eugen Seibold* layout and research expeditions. A) Side view layout of the *S/Y Eugen Seibold* (1: air inlet, 2: air laboratory, 3: meteorological station, 4: air sampler, 5: seawater inlet, 6: water laboratory). B) Cruise track of the *S/Y Eugen Seibold* from 2020 to 2023, colored by sampling year and month. Black stars are locations where samples for microbial analyses were taken. Circles are stations where vertical water profiles were sampled. Sampled oceanic provinces are outlined (ARCT: Atlantic Arctic, SARC: Atlantic Subarctic, NECS: Northeast Atlantic Shelves, NADR: North Atlantic Drift, NASE: North Atlantic Subtropical Gyral East, NATR: North Atlantic Tropical Gyral, CNRY: Canary Current Coastal, WTRA: Western Tropical Atlantic, GUIA: Guianas Coastal, CARB: Caribbean; Longhurst, 2007).

Subtask activities in numbers

- Cruises total 17 (6 in 2020, 3 in 2021, 6 in 2022, 2 in 2023)
- Samples total: 263

A comprehensive set of other parameters was sampled and measured during the cruises. An overview is given in Schiebel et al., 2024. Here, samples are listed which were sent for sequencing at Genoscope within the AtlantECO project targeting the 16S and 18S rRNA gene. Of the below samples, 98 were collected from surface waters (3 m water depth), 104 between 10 and 100 m water depth, and 43 below 100 m water depth. Once sequencing is finished, data accessible microbial community structure will be analyzed together with additional data (including additional sequencing data from underway water and air sampling) collected aboard *S/Y Eugen Seibold* and from publicly available databases.

Table 5.1 *Filter samples currently at Genoscope for sequencing of the 16S and 18S rRNA gene.*

Cruise ID	Year	Month	Departure	Arrival	Filter > 10 µm	Filter 3 - 10 µm	Filter 0.2 – 3 µm
ES20C04	2020	07	Seydisfjordur, Iceland	Vestmannaeyjar, Iceland	5	8	4

ES20C05	2020	07	Vestmannaeyjar, Iceland	Galway, Ireland		8	4
ES20C06	2020	08	Galway, Ireland	Azores, Portugal	5	10	4
ES20C07	2020	08	Azores, Portugal	Azores, Portugal	5	5	3
ES20C08	2020	09	Azores, Portugal	Madeira, Portugal	6	10	9
ES20C09	2020	11	Madeira, Portugal	Lanzarote, Marina Rubicon	5	5	5
ES21C03	2021	02	Gran Canaria, Spain	Lanzarote, Marina Rubicon	1	1	1
ES21C06	2021	04	Lanzarote, Marina Rubicon	Cape Verde, Mindelo	5	5	4
ES21C08	2021	05	Cape Verde, Mindelo	Cape Verde, Mindelo	6	20	4
ES22C12	2022	09/10	Baiona, Spain	Lanzarote, Marina Rubicon	4	4	4
ES22C13	2022	10	Lanzarote, Marina Rubicon	Lanzarote, Marina Rubicon	6	6	6
ES22C14	2022	10	Lanzarote, Marina Rubicon	Lanzarote, Marina Rubicon	6	6	6
ES22C15	2022	10	Lanzarote, Marina Rubicon	Lanzarote, Marina Rubicon	4	5	4
ES22C18	2022	12	Lanzarote, Marina Rubicon	Cape Verde, Mindelo	8	16	4
ES22C19	2022/ 2023	12/01	Cape Verde, Mindelo	Grenada, St. George's	0	13	0
ES23C01	2023	02	Grenada, St. George's	Aruba, Oranjestad	0	3	0
ES23C02	2023	02/03	Aruba, Renaissance Marina	Panama, Shelter Bay Marina	0	5	5

Key exploitable results that will be available in open access before the end of the project

Datasets

- Walter, D.; Aardema, H. M.; Calleja, M. Ll; Dragoneas, A.; Hrabe de Angelis, I.; Pöhlker, C.; Slagter, H. A.; Schiebel, R. (2023): Master track of Eugen Seibold cruise ES19C01 to ES21C14, PANGAEA, <https://www.pangaea.de/expeditions/bybasis/Eugen%20Seibold>
- Schiebel, R. (2024). Data from probing the open ocean with the research sail yacht Eugen Seibold [Dataset]. Edmond. <https://doi.org/10.17617/3.30MFES>
- Sequencing data of 2020/2021 expedition, BioProject accession PRJNA1148129 (<http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/bioproject/1148129>). To be released upon manuscript acceptance

Publications

- Hrabe de Angelis et al., submitted to PNAS, Microbial latitudinal diversity gradients and lineage-selective exchange between the Atlantic surface ocean and the lower atmosphere
- Schiebel, R., Aardema, H. M., Calleja, M. Ll., Dragoneas, A., Heins, L., Hrabe de Angelis, I., et al. (2024). Preface: Special issue on probing the open ocean with the research sailing Yacht Eugen Seibold for climate geochemistry. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, 129, e2023JD040581. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2023JD040581>

Flagship RV Alpha Crucis

The scientific focus of the expeditions onboard RV Alpha Crucis was to collect samples covering an important and yet underexplored region of the South Atlantic, including oceanic and coastal areas, to expand the worldwide microbiome database. Two cruises occurred onboard RV Alpha Crucis: the first, from July 28th to August 11th, 2022 and the second from March 21st to March 25th, 2023, covering the coordinates 24° - 34.5°S, 50.5° - 44.3°W. Eighteen stations were sampled in the first cruise and 5 stations for the second cruise in order to study unicellular eukaryotes, prokaryotes and viruses (i.e., 3 samples for each station). The samples are under processing by the UFSCar team aiming at DNA sequencing.

Flagship SA Agulhas II

The Southern Ocean Seasonal Experiment (SCALE) winter cruise 2022 started its mission from Cape Town on board SA Agulhas II for a period of 3 weeks from 11 July 2022 to 31 August 2022, covering coordinates Lat: -33.5406; Long: 18.253 – Lat: -59.40472; Long: -0.52032. The cruise was organized by the South African Polar Research Infrastructure (SAPRI) with the purpose to serve the scientific community involved in Southern Ocean research projects funded through the NRF (SANAP and other programmes). Our microbiomics team from the University of Pretoria was among the research groups that went on this mission to study the functional capacity and community structure dynamics of the Southern Ocean (SO) microbiota on a temporal and spatial scale using meta-omic approaches. The samples collected during the cruise were meant to cover several objectives which include:

- Assessing how the co-limitations of trace metals, specifically iron (Fe) and Manganese (Mg), influence microbial community composition and functionality using an omics approach combined with a trace metal profile.
- Assess the diversity of viruses in the Southern Ocean, and how these may contribute towards biogeochemical cycling.
- Determine how DMSP cycling genes and concentrations in the Southern Ocean provide an understanding towards the variable microbial physiological responses towards DMSP degradation.

Update on sample processing and data analysis:

Objective 1 – DNA has been extracted from all the 0.2 micron filters and these have recently been sent out for sequencing (to generate amplicon data).

Objective 2 – Viral filters have not been processed as yet.

Objective 3 – DMSP quantification, DNA extraction and shotgun metagenomics data have been generated and analysed for the DMSP project.

Flagship RSS Discovery

AMT cruises are multidisciplinary surveys of biology, chemistry, and physics oceanographic research, between the United Kingdom and destinations in the South Atlantic (Chile, Falkland Islands and South Africa). The Atlantic Ocean harbors diverse oceanographic provinces and least is known about the structure and abundance of niche specific microbial guilds and their adaptive metabolic lifestyles in these interesting oceanographic spaces. As part of the doctoral thesis Mayi from the University of Pretoria participated in the AMT30 (for a period of 6 weeks) with an aim to decipher some of these relevant but remaining unaddressed

microbial facets. AMT30 covered the coordinates from Lat. -46.85 and Long. -48.32 to Lat. 40.32 and Long. -16.55. During this transect 162 samples were collected (following standardized AtlantECO protocol) from 27 pre-dawn stations for metagenomics and transcriptomics analysis. I consistently targeted 3 depths, which is the surface (5 m), deep chlorophyll maximum (DCM) (varied across oceanic space) and mesopelagic zone (500 m) as the source of the sampling.

Samples for genomics analyses were collected alongside those for dimethylsulfoniopropionate (DMSP) and dimethylsulfoxonium propionate (DMSOP). Therefore, 486 samples were collected for total and particulate (3.0 μm and 0.2 μm) DMSP and DMSOP analyses. Although DMSP and DMSOP samples were only collected from the surface and DCM depths. This data will be inferred with complimentary metadata such as flow cytometry and nutrient data that was generated during the cruise. In addition to what is primarily for my thesis data, I did flocculation for virus filtrations from all stations and depths. I hope to split this virus work with someone else (fortunately in my lab we have experts for ocean viruses) to fasten the output. Also, I collected 54 samples eDNA analyses and I skipped other stations due to the shortage of sterivex cartridges and eDNA samples were given to Stephan for further downstream workflow.

All the measurements for DMSP and DMSOP have now been done. I have finished DNA and RNA extraction. We have sent all samples for 16s rRNA and ITS amplicon sequencing. I am expecting to receive the data somewhere in the middle of September 2023. I will be using this amplicon data as the markers to select samples for shotgun metagenomics and transcriptomics sequencing. I have also started with virus DNA extraction but this is not going steadily fast since I am still working on the metagenomics analyses from the SCALE cruise which I did last year (2022).

6 The all Atlantic Ocean Microbiome Sampling “day” (lead: EMBRC-ERIC)

The South America Ocean Sampling Day (SA-OSD) is a coordinated continental initiative that contributes to large-scale marine microbiome research by generating standardized, comparable molecular and environmental data across the South American coastline and Mexico (Figs. 6.1 and 6.2). Between 2022 and 2025, SA-OSD has consolidated a transnational network of research institutions, fostering collaboration, capacity building, and harmonized sampling efforts in coastal marine environments.

Within the project framework, SA-OSD aimed to strengthen regional participation in global ocean observing initiatives by implementing shared sampling protocols, centralized molecular analyses, and open data dissemination. The initiative focused on generating omics-based microbiome datasets (16S,18S rRNA, metagenomic) coupled with environmental metadata, enabling comparative analyses of bacterial and protistan communities across broad spatial and temporal scales.

Beyond data generation, SA-OSD played a key role in training students and early-career researchers, promoting methodological standardization, and enhancing data interoperability across institutions (Fig. 6.3). All activities were designed to ensure open access to the resulting datasets, reinforcing FAIR data principles and supporting long-term reuse by the scientific community.

Samples from the first two editions are currently biobanked at the respective sequencing centres, and will be analysed together with samples from the third edition. At some sites, additional samples were collected for microscopic determination of plankton and microplastics. Some sites also engaged with local schools and community members on the day of sampling to raise awareness about the marine microbiome. All sites will be encouraged to engage in outreach activities during the next editions.

Figure 6.1. Map of OSD sampling sites worldwide, including the OSD sites created during AtlantECO.

Figure 6.2. Map of SA-OSD sampling sites showing the spatial distribution of coastal stations sampled between 2022 and 2025 across South America and Mexico.

Figure 6.3. Photographic documentation of SA-OSD field sampling and sample processing, illustrating standardized coastal water collection and water filtration procedures.

Subtask activities in numbers

- Sampling campaigns: 4 coordinated annual SA-OSD campaigns
- Geographic coverage: 6 countries (Argentina, Brazil, Colombia, Chile, Uruguay, Mexico)
- Participating institutions: ~30 research institutions
- Sampling events: 4 Ocean Sampling Day events (2022–2025)
- Samples collected: 147 coastal marine samples
- Molecular analyses:
 - 16S rRNA gene amplicon sequencing (bacterial diversity)
 - 18S rRNA gene amplicon sequencing (protistan diversity)
- Environmental parameters measured:
 - Temperature
 - Chlorophyll
 - Bathymetry
 - Salinity
 - Nitrates
 - Phosphates
 - Dissolved oxygen
- Datasets generated and uploaded:
 - Bacterial diversity profiles
 - Protistan diversity profiles
 - Bacterial relative abundance tables
 - Protistan relative abundance tables
 - Associated environmental metadata

Key exploitable results already available in open access

At the time of reporting, no SA-OSD datasets have been released in open-access repositories. Data generation, curation, and quality control are currently ongoing, and all datasets produced within SA-OSD are planned to be released in open access following project timelines and data management policies.

Key exploitable results that will be available in open access before the end of the project

- Consolidated documentation and reporting materials to support future reuse of protocols, datasets, and analytical workflows
- 16S rRNA gene amplicon data for bacterial community diversity
- 18S rRNA gene amplicon data for protistan community diversity
- Standardized environmental metadata associated with each sampling site
- Comparative analyses of coastal bacterial and protistan community structure across South America and Mexico

At least one peer-reviewed scientific article describing regional patterns, methodological frameworks, and community-level insights derived from SA-OSD data.

Additional information can be found at the [SA-OSD](#) website.

Sample List and Institutions:

Country	Campaign	Sampling date	SiteID	Latitude	Longitude	City, State	Protocol	sample-id	RNA-later	Institution _acronym	Researcher
Brazil	2022	20220921		-23.00115	-42.005683	Arraial do Cabo, RJ	S02-200	SAMEA7937485	yes	IEAPM	Sávio H. CALAZANS e Lohengrim
Brazil	2022	20220923	PA8081	-0.604624	-47.500221	Belém, PA	S02-200	SAMEA7937486	yes	UFPA	JUSSARA MARTINELLI LEMOS
Brazil	2022	20221120	RN8889	-0.538543	-35.03795	Natal, RN	S02-200	SAMEA7937488	yes	UFRN	Ali Ger, Juliana Déo Dias e Maiara Menezes
Brazil	2022	20220923	BA9091	-16.417	-38.982	Porto Seguro, BA	S02-200	SAMEA7937490	yes	UFSB	THIAGO MAFRA
Brazil	2022	20220923	PA 8081	-0.5916	-47.3116	Belém, PA	S02-200	SAMEA7937480	yes	UFRA	XIOMARA GARCIA
Brazil	2022	20220921	SPU	-23.3112	-45.0512	São Paulo, SP	S02-200	SAMEA7937498	yes	USP	Rubens Mendes Lopes e Gleice Santos Souza
Brazil	2022	20220921	SC-0001	-27.2805	-48.4227	Florianópolis, SC	S02-200	SAMEA7937500	yes	UFSC	Andrea Freire e Andrea Green
Brazil	2022	20220921	PSC-3940	-27.2799	-48.2848	Florianópolis, SC	S02-200	SAMEA7906439	yes	UFSC	Andrea Freire e Andrea Green
Brazil	2022	20220921		-8.761335	-35.09079	Recife, PE	S02-200	SAMEA7937502	yes	UFRPE	MAURO
Brazil	2022	20220921		-3.7223	-38.4819	Fortaleza, CE	S02-200	SAMEA7937504	yes	Labomar-UFC	Marcelo Soares / Tatiane Garcia / Tallita Tavares / Hortência Barroso
Brazil	2022	20220921	SPO2	-23.990585	-46.3095	Santos, SP	S02-200	SAMEA7937506	yes	UNIFESP	José Juan Barrera Alba

Country	Campaign	Sampling date	SiteID	Latitude	Longitude	City, State	Protocol	sample-id	RNA-later	Institution _acronym	Researcher
Brazil	2022	20220921		-29.954644	-50.1084	Imbé, RS	S02-200	SAMEA794 3488	yes	CECLIMAR/ UFRGS	Haig They
Argentina	2022	20221124		-42.4709	-64.533	Puerto Madryn, Chubut	S02-200	SAMEA794 3514	yes	IBIOMAR,CE NPAT-CONI CET	Paulina Fermani, Mariana Lozada
Argentina	2022	20221128		-41.02245	-62.7963	Las Grutas, Río Negro	S02-200	SAMEA794 3496	yes	ESCiMar-UN Co	Hünicken Leandro
Argentina	2022	20221125		-40.737	-64.9051	Las Grutas, Río Negro	S02-200	SAMEA794 3492	yes	ESCiMar-UN Co	Saad Juan Francisco
Argentina	2022	20221125		-40.871467	-65.07775	San Antonio Oeste, Río Negro	S02-200	SAMEA794 3494	yes	ESCiMar-UN Co	Saad Juan Francisco
Panamá	2022	20221123	WQSTR1	9.348	-82.26594	Panamá	S>02	SAMEA790 9627	No	Smrthsonia n	Valentina Cardona
Argentina	2023	20231014	LG8586	-40.871967	-65.07775	San Antonio Oeste, Río Negro	S02-200	SAMEA790 9486	yes	ESCiMar-UN Co	Saad Juan Francisco
Argentina	2023	20230928	SA8384	-40.737108	-64.90524	Las Grutas, Río Negro	S02-200	SAMEA790 9483	yes	ESCiMar-UN Co	Saad Juan Francisco
Argentina	2023	20230929	PE	-42.4709	-64.533	Puerto Madryn, Chubut	S02-200	SAMEA790 9477		IBIOMAR,CE NPAT-CONI CET	Paulina Fermani, Mariana Lozada
Argentina	2023	20231002	EGI	-43.357	-64.987	Rawson-Ch ubut	S>02	SAMEA790 9479	yes	EFPU/CONI CET	Macarena Soledad Valiñas

Country	Campaign	Sampling date	SiteID	Latitude	Longitude	City, State	Protocol	sample-id	RNA-later	Institution _acronym	Researcher
Colombia	2023					Cartagena, Bolivar	S02-200	SAMEA790 9447		USinú	Patricia Romero Murillo, Yurina
Colombia	2023	20230920	UR	8.4645358	-76.802315	Apartadó, Antioquia	S02-300	SAMEA790 9449	yes	UdeA	Lina Zapata, Carolina García , Juan Pablo Niño
Colombia	2023	20230920	UR	8.4645358	-76.802315	Apartadó, Antioquia	S02-300	SAMEA790 9450	yes	UdeA	Lina Zapata, Carolina García , Juan Pablo Niño
Colombia	2023	20230921	SUC	9.4241127	-75.634437	Coveñas Sucre	S02-300	SAMEA790 9446	yes	USucre	Aldo F. Combariza Montañez
Colombia	2023	20230921	SUC	9.4241127	-75.634437	Coveñas Sucre	S02-300	SAMEA790 9445	yes	USucre	Aldo F. Combariza Montañez
Colombia	2023	20230926	BBC	11.0554	-74.85388	Puerto Colombia, Atlantico	S>02	SAMEA790 9443	yes	ULibre	Clara Gutiérrez Castañeda, Beatriz Barraza Amador
Colombia	2023	20230926	BBC	11.0554	-74.85388	Puerto Colombia, Atlantico	S>02			ULibre	
Colombia	2023	20230921	MA	11.325277	-74.133833	Santa Marta, Magdalena	S02-300	SAMEA790 9451	yes	INVEMAR	Karen Ayala, Catalina Arteaga, Vanessa Yepes, Lyda Catro
Colombia	2023	20230921	MA	11.325277	-74.133833	Santa Marta, Magdalena	S02-300	SAMEA790 9452	yes	INVEMAR	Karen Ayala, Catalina Arteaga, Vanessa Yepes, Lyda Catro

Country	Campaign	Sampling date	SiteID	Latitude	Longitude	City, State	Protocol	sample-id	RNA-later	Institution _acronym	Researcher
Colombia	2023	20230921	MA	11.325277	-74.133833	Santa Marta, Magdalena	S02-300			INVEMAR	
Colombia	2023	20230921	MA	11.325277	-74.133833	Santa Marta, Magdalena	S02-300			INVEMAR	
Brazil	2023	20230921	LABOMAR-UFC	-3.7223	-38.4919	Fortaleza, Ceará	S02-200	SAMEA790 9471		Labomar-UFC	Tallita Cruz Lopes Tavares, Hortência de Sousa Barroso
Brazil	2023	20230921	UFRGS	-29.954644	-50.108406	Imbé, RS	S>02	SAMEA794 3490	yes	CECLIMAR/UFRGS	Ng Haig They, Nátali Kegler Pivato Gonçalves, Lucas Teixeira de Oliveira
Brazil	2023	20230921	SC6465	-27.1678	-48.4224	Florianópolis, SC	S02-200	SAMEA790 6465	yes	UFSC	Andrea Freire, Andrea Green e Érica Becker
Brazil	2023	20230920	SPS	-23.996833	-46.324339	Santos, SP	S02-200	SAMEA790 9469	yes	UNIFESP	José Juan Barrera Alba
Brazil	2023	20230920	SPUBA	-23.5194	-45.1049	Ubatuba, SP, Brasil	S02-200	SAMEA790 9463	yes	Instituto Oceanográfico - USP	Mariana Rodrigues dos Santos
Brazil	2023	20231001	PASAL	-0.593889	-47.312222	Belém, Pará	S02-200	SAMEA790 9461		ISARH	Xiomara Franchesca Garcia Díaz e Paula Nepomuceno Campos
Brazil	2023	20210915	PELD	-8.7669444	-35.093888	Recife, PE	S02-200	SAMEA790 9459		UFRPE	Mauro

7 The all Atlantic Sail-4-Science (lead: SU)

The aim of subtask 4.2.3 was to generate and implement a light version of AtlantECO's protocols to be carried out by citizen scientists along latitudinal and longitudinal routes across the Atlantic.

The first phase of the subtask focused on the development of smaller, affordable, easy-to-use instruments for genomics and imaging, and on the generation of simple yet comprehensive protocols to be used for data collection for citizen science. The second phase of the subtask focused on the deployment, feedback collection and subsequent improvement of the protocols and instruments in an iterative process.

The first phase of the project (2020-2021) has been dedicated to improving the instrumentation. Taking advantage of Tara's Atlantic crossing in December 2020, instruments for both plankton collection (High Speed Net, HSN) and plankton imaging (PlanktoScope) were embarked and compared to their state-of-the-art commercial equivalents present on board (decknet and Flowcam respectively). The results obtained during Tara's transect have been published in 2022 in open access (Mériguet et al, 2022). The problems encountered and the feedback obtained from Tara's sailors, used as first citizen scientists, led to the development of the final versions of the HSN and PlanktoScope to be deployed in AtlantECO. These versions were further tested for 1) technical performance, with deployment of the instruments in several laboratories participating in AtlantECO (Lombard's and Lopes' labs) and 2) usability, with a workshop organized in collaboration with the Institut Nicod for Cognitive Science (Paris), aimed at testing instruments usability along with a first version of protocols for citizen science.

From 2022 to 2024, 30 citizen scientists (ranging from engineering students to professional sailors, psychologists, finance officers and graphic designers, a.o.) have operated onboard their boats to collect data on plankton with the S4S lighter protocols and instruments, for a total of ~200 samples (Figs. 7.1 and 7.2).

In addition to the samples, feedback on the experience was collected from the citizens who participated in the project. This feedback will be analyzed in the context of a doctoral thesis at the Ecole Normale Supérieure of Paris focusing on the interaction between science and society and on how citizen science affects the cognition of the ocean in the participants.

Thanks to the actions undertaken by the subtask 4.2.3 of AtlantECO, long-term collaborations have been established between the civil society (e.g Ocean Trotter, South Wind Shipyard) and the scientific laboratories of AtlantECO (Sorbonne University, Cape Town University) that will continue beyond AtlantECO.

Figure 7.1. Top left: the different routes taken by the citizens involved in the S4S program. Top right: a sailor proudly showing the HSN during training. Bottom left: the last version of the PlanktoScope and of the HSN. Bottom right: world renowned French sailor Isabelle Autissier, involved in the S4S program, learning to use systems for genomics membrane preparation.

As an additional result, one of the instruments developed in the first phase (the PlanktoScope) has been adopted by several laboratories implicated in AtlantECO (Lombard's, Lopes', Rocke's, Freire's labs) as a routine instrument for plankton imaging. Overall, the work carried out in subtask 4.2.3 highlighted both the complexity and the potential of the citizen science approach and stressed the importance of training and of clear and usable instructions for successful data collection. We have learned a great deal on the difficulties of carrying out high-quality citizen science of the ocean, in particular concerning data quality and metadata reliability, and on the solutions we can implement to face these challenges.

AtlantECO has allowed to set the basis for a stronger, more reliable citizen science of the ocean for the years to come.

Subtask activities

- Optimization of low-tech instruments for citizen science
- Tests aimed at both technical performance and usability
- Definition and refinement of a basic kit set for citizen science of plankton
- Production and optimization of a kit of protocols for citizen science of plankton
- Training of citizens to plankton collection and imaging
- Follow-up during deployment
- Oral and written feedback collection
- Data and metadata collection

Subtask results

- 11 cruises (each composed of multiple legs)
- 4 quadrants of the Atlantic ocean covered
- 34 citizens trained to S4S protocols
- 180 stations sampled
- 105 DNA samples collected
- 560.000 plankton images collected
- Definition of a basic kit and set of protocols for citizen science of plankton
- Feedback from the citizens that will serve as the basis for a doctoral thesis in epistemology at the ENS
- Long-term collaborations created between participating citizens and laboratories

Subtask results in open access

- 560.000 images deposited in EcoTaxa (open access database)
- Published article: Mériguet et al, 2022 ([10.3389/fmars.2022.916025](https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2022.916025))
- Published protocol for PlanktoScope operation: Kostyrka et al, 2024 ([dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.bp2l6bq3zggq/v3](https://doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.bp2l6bq3zggq/v3))

In the first phase, we developed new affordable plankton sampling (HSN net), genomics (Lamprey kit) and imaging (Planktoscope microscope) for citizen science, aimed either at genomics or morphological studies. Sampling and imaging kits were tested along the first transect of Tara, and the results were published (<https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fmars.2022.916025>). Subsequently, the kits were tested with a group of 5 “seatizens” to test their ergonomics and usability, and 5 units of the Planktoscope (the portable in-flux automated imaging device in the kit) were sent to AtlantECO partners laboratories for further technical evaluation.

Based on the feedback received, the final version v.2.6 of the Planktoscope was established for deployment onboard citizen boats.

The first deployments of the citizen science kits took place between November 2022 and August 2023, onboard 3 “seatizen” sailing boats: 1) Pilourson, a 9m sailing boat with onboard an engineering student, a primary school teacher, a video director and an engineer, none with background in oceanography, on a route between Norway and France ; 2) Re’Alizé, a crew of 6 engineering students, none with background in oceanography, who embarked on a North-Atlantic loop with their 12m sailing boat, and 3) Ada, a 14m sailing boat with onboard a professional sailor, a professional alpinist, a carpenter and an IT manager, on a route between Greenland and France.

Training was carried out onboard each sailing boat, with at least 1 member (Pilourson) or all members (ReAlizés, Ada) of the crew.

After each deployment, a questionnaire was sent to the “seatizens” who participated in the sampling activity, and oral feedback was collected, aimed at 1) listing the technical problems that might have occurred with the instruments, 2) listing potential improvements to the instruments, protocols and manuals, 3) understanding the challenges of using the scientific equipments on board a sailing boat, 4) understanding the challenges (often non-obvious for a community of professional scientists) of obtaining high-quality data from citizen science.

Finally, organisation of additional routes and examination of new “seatizens” candidates for other Atlantic routes is ongoing.

Figure 7.2. Sail4Science routes undertaken up to September 2023.

8 A Continuous Plankton Recorder (CPR) survey (lead: MBA)

The establishment of a transatlantic Continuous Plankton Recorder (CPR) route between Brazil and South Africa began in early in 2021 when the Marine Biological Association’s (MBA) CPR Survey team rigged the container ship *Lodur* (IMO9219381) to tow a CPR owned by South Africa’s Department of Forestry, Fisheries and the Environment (DFFE) on a route between Brazil and South Africa. Sampling started on the 23rd of October 2021 when the *MV Lodur* deployed the CPR with the first internal cassette. After the initial crossing, 3 other successful crossings followed in 2022, totaling 4 crossings and sampling 11,722 nautical miles (nm). In 2023, the container ship *Lodur* was reassigned to a different route and a new vessel, the container ship *Northern Democrat* (IMO9391787), was contracted by MBA, equipped by MBA and DFFE, and another two transects (1 successful) were conducted with this ship (Fig. 8.1). In December 2023, the *Northern Democrat* was also reassigned and the process of approaching the owners of a new ship via Hapag Loyd was made by MBA. The container ship *Mirador Express* (IMO 9243174) was contracted in April 2024 and was rigged to resume sampling later in 2024 and 2025, but the unfortunate theft of the CPR body prevented further collection of samples on this route. A shorter route between South Africa and Tristan da Cunha was also sampled in September 2024 (and September 2025) on the DFFE research vessel *S.A. Agulhas II* (IMO9577135), and should be continued, until the full Brazil – South Africa route can be resumed.

Figure 8.1. Overview of the Continuous Plankton Recorder (CPR) survey routes within the South Atlantic Ocean Region as part of the AtlantECO Project. Sections indicate CPR internal cassettes used.

Overall, a total of 17,661 nm nautical miles (nm) were sampled over 6 crossings with a CPR between Brazil and South Africa during AtlantECO, collecting over 2,124 samples (Table 8.1). All samples were retrieved by DFFE personnel in South Africa and sent to Universidade Federal do Rio Grande (FURG) in Brazil for analysis according to the methodology detailed in Esquivel-Garrote and Muxagata (2023) and Esquivel-Garrote et al. (2023).

In summary, upon arrival at the lab, the CPR silk mesh was initially unrolled, measured and cut into 20 nm intervals. The Phytoplankton Colour Index (PCI) was then estimated for each 20nm section. The first and last 5nm segments of each 20nm section were cut and all organisms present were washed into a counting chamber and identified to the lowest taxonomic resolution possible. The middle 10nm segments (Fig. 8.2) were archived for future CPR comparisons with Northern Atlantic standards. Overall, 50% of the collected samples, or every other sample, were archived as 10 nm samples.

Table 8.1. Dates and number of sections and samples retrieved on each transect from 2021 to 2024.

Route	Date	Section Codes	Valid Sections	Distance	5nm samples	10 nm samples
1	Oct 21	1 BSA to 8 BSA	1, 2, 3, 5, 7, 8.	2,364	234	120
2	Jan 22	9 BSA to 16 BSA	11, 12, 13, 14, 15.	2,261	219	115
3	Jul 22	17 BSA to 24 BSA	17, 18, 21, 22.	3,548	173	87
4	Dec 22	25 BSA to 32 BSA	26, 27, 29, 31.	3,549	207	104
5	Jun 23	33 BSA to 40 BSA	No valid samples	2,922	0	0
6	Sep 23	41 BSA to 48 BSA	41,43,44,45,46,48	3,017	221	109
7	Sep 24	SA to Tristan	Still under evaluation	1,468	~146	~73
8	Sep 25	SA to Tristan	Still under evaluation	--	--	--

Figure 8.2. Example of CPR sample distribution. The 5nm samples are processed, and the 10 nm samples are archived (total number of samples are calculated based on 5nm intervals).

A total of 1054 samples of 5nm were processed, and preliminary results were presented during GA2023, GA 2024 and GA 2025. So far, with more than 80% of the samples processed, a total of 186 taxa (95 species) have been counted and identified (Table 8.2).

Table 8.2. Zooplanktonic taxa found in CPR samples collected between Brazil and South Africa.

Phylum Myzozoa	<i>Clausocalanus</i> spp.	<i>Corycaeus crassiusculus</i>
<i>Trinos</i> spp.	<i>Ctenocalanus citer</i>	<i>Corycaeus speciosus</i>
Phylum Foraminifera	<i>Ctenocalanus</i> spp.	<i>Corycaeus latus</i>
Foraminifera not id	<i>Rhinocalanus nasutus</i>	<i>Onchocorycaeus</i>
Foraminifera sp1	<i>Rhinocalanus comutus</i>	<i>giesbrechti</i>
Foraminifera sp2	<i>Rhinocalanus</i> spp.	<i>Onchocorycaeus</i> spp.
<i>Globorotalia</i> sp.	<i>Subeucalanus pileatus</i>	<i>Urocorycaeus lautus</i>
<i>Globorotalia</i> spp.	<i>Subeucalanus</i> spp.	<i>Lubbockia aculeata</i>
Phylum Retaria	<i>Pseudocalanidae</i> not id	<i>Agetus typicus</i>
Radiolaria not id	<i>Euchirella messinensis</i>	<i>Farranula concinna</i>
Phylum Cnidaria	<i>Euchirella</i> sp.	<i>Farranula gracilis</i>
Cnidaria not id	<i>Euchaetidae</i> not id	<i>Farranula rostrata</i>
Siphonophorae not id	<i>Euchaeta</i> spp.	<i>Farranula</i> spp.
<i>Eudoxoides mitra</i>	<i>Euchaeta marina</i>	<i>Saphirina angusta</i>
Phylum Bryozoa	<i>Paraeuchaeta</i> sp.	<i>Saphirina intestinalis</i>
Bryozoa larvae not id	<i>Undeuchaeta plumosa</i>	<i>Saphirina aurantens sinuicauda</i>
Phylum Annelida	<i>Scolecithrix danae</i>	<i>Saphirina gastrica</i>
Class Polychaeta	<i>Scolecithrix</i> spp.	<i>Saphirina nigromaculata</i>
Polychaeta not id	<i>Scolecithricella dentata</i>	<i>Saphirina</i> spp.
<i>Alciopinidae</i> not id	<i>Scolecithricella</i> spp.	<i>Capilia mirabilis</i>
Phylum Mollusca	<i>Temora stylifera</i>	<i>Capilia</i> spp.
Gastropoda veliger not id	<i>Temora turbinata</i>	Class Thecostraca
Bivalvia veliger not id	<i>Temora</i> spp.	Cirripedia Nauplii not id
Pteropoda not id	<i>Metridia</i> sp.	Cirripedia Cypris not id
<i>Cephalobranchia macrochaeta</i>	<i>Pleuromamma abdominalis</i>	Class Ostracoda
<i>Limacina</i> spp.	<i>Pleuromamma piseki</i>	Ostracoda not id
Atlantidae not id	<i>Pleuromamma gracilis</i>	Class Branchiopoda
Atlanta sp.	<i>Pleuromamma xiphias</i>	Order Cladocera
Phylum Arthropoda	<i>Pleuromamma</i> spp.	Cladocera not id
Crustacea not id	<i>Centropages longicornis</i>	<i>Pseudoevadne terestina</i>
Crustacea egg not id	<i>Centropages brachiatus</i>	<i>Evadne spinifera</i>
Crustacea Nauplii not id	<i>Centropages calaninus</i>	<i>Penilia avicostis</i>
Class Copepoda	<i>Centropages elongatus</i>	<i>Rodan Leuckarti</i>
Copepoda nauplii not id	<i>Centropages gracilis</i>	<i>Rodan</i> spp.
Order Calanoida	<i>Centropages violaceus</i>	Class Malacostraca
Calanoida not id	<i>Centropages velificatus</i>	Malacostraca not id
<i>Calanus agulhensis</i>	<i>Centropages furcatus</i>	Egg not id
<i>Calanus australis</i>	<i>Centropages</i> spp.	Order Amphipoda
<i>Calanus similimus</i>	<i>Lucicutia flavicornis</i>	Amphipoda not id
<i>Calanus</i> spp.	<i>Lucicutia gemina</i>	Hyperiidae not id
<i>Acrocalanus longicornis</i>	<i>Lucicutia</i> sp.	Phronima not id
<i>Acrocalanus</i> spp.	<i>Haloptilus</i> sp.	Order Mysida
<i>Mesocalanus tenuicornis</i>	<i>Heterorhabdus</i> sp.	Mysida not id
<i>Calanoides carinatus</i>	<i>Candacia simplex</i>	Order Euphausiacea
<i>Neocalanus</i> spp.	<i>Candacia bispinosa</i>	Euphausiacea not id
<i>Neocalanus tonsus</i>	<i>Candacia pachydactyla</i>	<i>Euphausia</i> sp.
<i>Neocalanus gracilis</i>	<i>Candacia curta</i>	<i>Euphausia similis</i>
<i>Neocalanus robustior</i>	<i>Candacia varicans</i>	Order Decapoda
<i>Nannocalanus minor</i>	<i>Candacia</i> spp.	Decapoda larvae not id
<i>Nannocalanus</i> spp.	<i>Pontellina plumata</i>	Luciferidae not id
<i>Urdinula vulgari</i>	<i>Pontellidae</i> not id	Sergestidae not id
<i>Urdinula</i> spp.	<i>Calanopia americana</i>	Phylum Chaetognatha
<i>Eucalanidae</i> not id	<i>Calanopia</i> sp.	Chaetognatha not id
<i>Eucalanus tivalinus</i>	<i>Acartia danae</i>	<i>Flaccisagitta</i> spp.
<i>Paracalanus sewelli</i>	<i>Acartia nealigens</i>	<i>Sagitta</i> spp.
<i>Paracalanus</i> spp.	<i>Acartia lilleboroi</i>	<i>Serratiasagitta serratodentata</i>
<i>Paracalanus aculeatus</i>	<i>Acartia</i> spp.	Phylum Chordata
<i>Paracalanus pacvus</i>	<i>Acartiella</i> sp.	Class Appendicularia
<i>Acrocalanus longicornis</i>	<i>Calanidae</i> spp.	Order Copelata
<i>Acrocalanus</i> spp.	Order Harpacticoida	Appendicularia not id
<i>Calocalanus pavo</i>	<i>Glytemnestra scutellata</i>	<i>Oikopleura dioica</i>
<i>Calocalanus plumosus</i>	<i>Eutermia acutifrons</i>	Class Thaliacea
<i>Calocalanus styliremis</i>	<i>Microsetella rosea</i>	Order Salpida
<i>Calocalanus</i> spp.	<i>Miracia efferata</i>	Salpida not id
<i>Mecynocera clausi</i>	<i>Miracia</i> sp.	Order Doliolida
<i>Clausocalanidae</i> not id	<i>Macrosetella gracilis</i>	Doliolida not id
<i>Clausocalanus arcuicornis</i>	Order Cyclopoida	Order Pyrosomatida
<i>Clausocalanus brevipes</i>	<i>Oithona</i> spp.	Pyrosomatida not id
<i>Clausocalanus furcatus</i>	<i>Oithona plumifera</i>	Osteichthyes
<i>Clausocalanus inagens</i>	<i>Oncaea mediterranea</i>	Fish larvae not id
<i>Clausocalanus mastioophorus</i>	<i>Oncaea venusta</i>	<i>Leptocephala</i> larvae not id
<i>Clausocalanus parapergens</i>	<i>Oncaea media</i>	
<i>Clausocalanus paululus</i>	<i>Oncaea</i> spp.	
	<i>Corycaeus</i> spp.	

Remarkable differences were registered in the amount of organisms collected between transects, with higher abundances being recorded during the winter crossings (Fig. 8.3).

Figure 8.3. Zooplankton abundances per 5 nm samples on the CPR route between Brazil and South Africa (shaded areas indicate sections where internals failed and blank sections could indicate missing data, still under analysis or areas not sampled on shorter transects).

On all crossings, Copepoda was the most abundant group, followed by Chaetognatha, Euphausiacea and Foraminifera. Abundances of these groups were different between sections (Fig. 8.3). Samples collected near the Brazilian coast up to the Rio Grande Rise were the most diverse, comprising six of the taxonomic groups found. The Middle Atlantic section was characterized mostly by Copepoda and Chaetognatha (Fig. 8.4). The sections near the South African coast exhibited the highest number of recorded species, with the copepods *Neocalanus tonsus* and *Pleuromamma piseki* being most abundant.

Figure 8.4. Relative contribution of the main zooplanktonic groups per 5 nm samples on the CPR route between Brazil and South Africa (shaded areas indicate sections where internals failed and blank sections could indicate missing data, still under analysis or areas not sampled on shorter transects).

Microplastic fibers found on CPR mesh were also recorded and are presented in Figure 8.5.

Figure 8.5. Total microplastic fibers found in 5nm CPR samples collected between Brazil and South Africa.

Challenges with customs and specific forms delayed the arrival of the samples at FURG. The Research Foundation (FAURG) that supports the Federal University of Rio Grande, together with the Department of Forestry, Fisheries and the Environment of South Africa (DFFE), eventually resolved the importation problems (customs and specific forms) of the samples, and all samples including those from the new Tristan short route only arrived in mid-August 2025. To Date, ~80% of all predicted samples (5nm) were analyzed. A Master's dissertation using some of those samples was completed, and a paper is under revision. A PhD study was initiated in 2025 which will include all data collected, and at least three papers will be prepared.

Summary:

- A total of 17,661 nm were sampled within AtlantECO during 6 successful transatlantic crossings
- 1054 samples (5nm) were processed in the zooplankton laboratory at FURG.
- 535 samples (10nm) were archived for further comparison analysis.
- 186 taxa (95 species) were counted and identified so far.
- A new species was recorded for the eastern South Atlantic.

Capacity building:

- A Master's degree dissertation was finalized based on the results of the first crossing (corrections on a paper submitted in 2025 are under revision to be re-submitted).
 - A PhD study was started in 2025 to work with all the data.
 - A Scientific Initiation Undergraduate student was trained in CPR sample processing and identification
- A CPR and Imaging workshop was held in Cape Town in September 2025, following the PHOCIS workshop, where Brazilian and SA personnel were able to interact.

Table 8.3. Number of 5 and 10 nm samples retrieved from 2021 to 2023 and their processing stage

Transect	Date	Number of samples	10nm archive	5nm samples	Processed
1	Oct 21	88	22	44	100%
1	Oct 21	76	19	39	100%
1	Oct 21	81	20	41	100%
1	Oct 21	0	0	0	Void
1	Oct 21	75	18	37	100%
1	Oct 21	0	0	0	Void
1	Oct 21	75	20	39	100%
1	Oct 21	78	20	38	100%
2	Jan 22	0	0	0	Void
2	Jan 22	0	0	0	Void
2	Jan 22	89	44	45	100%
2	Jan 22	93	46	47	100%
2	Jan 22	95	48	47	100%
2	Jan 22	92	46	46	100%
2	Jan 22	92	46	46	100%
2	Jan 22	0	0	0	Void
3	Jul 22	84	42	42	100%
3	Jul 22	101	50	51	100%
3	Jul 22	0	0	0	Void
3	Jul 22	0	0	0	Void
3	Jul 22	90	45	45	100%
3	Jul 22	90	45	45	100%
3	Jul 22	0	0	0	Void
3	Jul 22	0	0	0	Void
4	Dec 22	0	0	0	Void
4	Dec 22	90	45	45	100%
4	Dec 22	94	47	47	100%
4	Dec 22	0	0	0	Void
4	Dec 22	91	46	45	100%
4	Dec 22	0	0	0	Void
4	Dec 22	90	45	45	100%
4	Dec 22	0	0	0	Void
5	Jun 23	0	0	0	Void
5	Jun 23	0	0	0	Void
5	Jun 23	0	0	0	Void

Transect	Date	Number of samples	10nm archive	5nm samples	Processed
5	Jun 23	0	0	0	Void
5	Jun 23	0	0	0	Void
5	Jun 23	0	0	0	Void
5	Jun 23	0	0	0	Void
5	Jun 23	0	0	0	Void
7	Sep 23	87	21	44	100%
7	Sep 23	0	0	0	Void
7	Sep 23	72	18	36	100%
7	Sep 23	68	17	34	100%
7	Sep 23	73	18	37	100%
7	Sep 23	73	18	37	100%
7	Sep 23	67	17	33	5%
7	Sep 23	0	0	0	Void

9 Genomics, Carbon and Plastic analysis of Moored Sediment Trap samples

In Task 4.2.5 NOC Team analysed the time-series samples from moored sediment traps deployed at 3000 m depth at three locations in the Atlantic Ocean (NOG, SOG, PAP; Figure 9.1) to deliver new data and knowledge about magnitude and characteristics (composition and morphology) of downward flux of microplastics (1 μm – 1 mm; MPs) and potential mechanisms facilitating their transport to depth, specifically aggregation of MPs with particulate organic matter (here as particulate organic carbon (POC)). The collection period at all three sites covered 2009-2016. For each deployment year, two samples of high-flux events and two samples of low-flux events were selected based on the measured dry weight flux (PAP samples) and estimated volume flux (NOG and SOG samples). Elevated and low flux events were based on $> |30\%|$ change in flux relative to annual average. In total, 96 samples were analysed for MPs and POC (32 samples per site and per parameter). An effective methodology was developed to extract MPs from the complex mixture of natural sinking particles preserved in buffered formalin solution, which was described in deliverable 4.2.5 (Sep 2023).

The analysis and interpretation of the MP dataset are in progress. The provisional results revealed high spatial and temporal variability in magnitude and composition of downward MP flux at all three sites. Over 150 different polymer types (thermoplastics, thermosets, and elastomers) were identified in all the samples; additives, plasticisers, paints, and adhesives were also detected.

The dataset from PAP is currently the most complete with regards to data analysis and interpretation. MP flux composition at PAP was dominated by Polyethylene-Polypropylene composite MPs which were detected in ca. 70% of samples. Other most discarded polymers, such as Polypropylene, Polyethylene, Polyurethanes, and polyesters were in about 40% of the PAP samples. The average total MP flux during high POC flux events at PAP was significantly higher than during the periods when POC flux was low (@high POC flux = 411 ± 690 MP particles $\text{m}^{-2} \text{d}^{-1}$; @low POC flux = 50 ± 79 MP particles $\text{m}^{-2} \text{d}^{-1}$) (Figure 9.1 A). A strong positive correlation was observed between fluxes of MPs and concurrent fluxes of POC ($R^2=0.63$, $p<0.01$; Fig. 9.2 B). This suggests that downward flux of POC/organic matter could be an important transport mechanism for MPs to the deep ocean.

In the next 12 months, the NOC Team will complete the analysis and interpretation of the remaining dataset (mainly NOG and SOG) as well as the assessment of inter-basin spatio-temporal variability of total and polymer-specific MP fluxes in relation to POC flux. Mass fluxes of the major polymer types detected at three sites will also be estimated following the existing methods (e.g. Pabortsava and Lampitt 2020, and/or NOMME: Number of Microplastics and Mass Estimation using LDIR Tool (Fuente et al., 2025) developed in EU LABPLAS). At least one manuscript will be submitted for publication in a peer-reviewed journal by the end of 2026 (provisional title: Sinking plastic snow - how microplastics get to the deep ocean). Given the breadth and complexity of the flux data generated other manuscripts will be developed in a longer term.

Figure 9.1. Location of the moored sediment traps (yellow triangles) deployed by NOC in the Atlantic Ocean. Figure adapted from Pabortsava et al. (2017)

Figure 9.2. Example of microplastic (MP) fluxes (number of MP particles $\text{m}^{-2} \text{d}^{-1}$) measured at PAP. A. Average MP flux to 3000 m depth at PAP during low and high POC flux events measured in 2009-2016. B. Correlation between POC and MP fluxes at PAP site.

Subtask activities related to moored sediment trap work in numbers (#cruises; sites; deployments; experiments; samples; analyses; parameters; data). Cruises on which mooring deployment and exchange took place are summarised in Table 9.1.

Table 9.1. Cruises during which sediment traps were deployed and recovered. Trap deployment number is indicated with a numbered letter T in parentheses. (*) denotes attempted recovery. At NOG, trap T75 was deployed from 2015 till 2017.

Deployment year	Cruise ID (Deployment-Recovery)		
	PAP	NOG	SOG
2009	D334-D341 (T54)	D334-D344 (T55)	JR186-JR215 (T53)
2010	D341-CE1005 (T57)	D344-D359 (T58)	JR215-JC053 (T56)
2011	CE1005-JC062 (T60)	D359-JC064 (T61)	JC053-D371*
2012	JC071-JC085 (T65)	JC064-D382 (T63)	D371-JC079 (T64)
2013	JC085-JC087 (T68)	D382-JC103 (T66)	JC079-BAS ship (T67)
2014	JC087 - M108 (T71)	JC103 - tbc (T69)	BAS ship – JR303 (T70)
2015	DY032-DY050 (T73)	tbc (T75)	JR303-JR15-1 (T72)
2016	DY050-DY077 (T76)	tbc (T75)	JR15-1 - tbc (T74)

Samples. In total 96 sediment trap samples (excl. blanks) collected between 2009-2016 were processed and analysed for POC. This involved: 1. Measuring volume material in the trap cups; 2. wet-splitting samples (trap cups) into 1/8 volumetric splits; 3. picking of zooplankton (swimmers) from a 1/8 split (per sample) under a dissecting microscope, 4. filtration of the material onto 0.8 µm GFF/filter; 5. Measuring mass of filtered material; 6. Removing inorganic carbon from the filtered material via acid-fuming; 7. Pelleting of the acid fumed samples for POC analysis; 8. Determination of organic carbon content using CHN analysis.

In total 96 sediment trap samples (excl. blanks) collected between 2009-2016 were processed and analysed for MPs. This involved: Measuring volume material in the trap cups; 2. wet-splitting samples (trap cups) into 1/8 volumetric splits; 3. Removal/reduction of natural organic and inorganic material via series of chemical digestions and physical (density) separation; 4. Filtration of the material remaining post-digestion and density separation onto 0.8 µm silver filters (some samples required multiple filters); 5. Detection of MPs via Fourier-Transform Infrared Imaging; 6. Polymer identification, quantification and characterisation.

Parameters and Data

- Dry weight/mass flux
- POC flux
- total MP flux (by particle count and mass)
- Polymer-specific MP flux (by particle count and mass)
- Polymer types of individual MPs
- 2D characteristics of individual MPs (size, area, aspect ratio, etc.)

After quality control, these data will be made publicly available at the British Oceanographic Data Centre (BODC) no later than two years after the end of AtlantECO, i.e. 2027-09-01.

Key exploitable results already available in open access (datasets citations, articles citations, other resources)

- Datasets of dry weight/mass flux, POC flux at PAP (2009-2016) and NOG (2009) and SOG (2009-2010) available from the British Oceanographic Data Centre (BODC);
- Publications: Lampitt, R. S., et al. "Deep ocean particle flux in the Northeast Atlantic over the past 30 years: carbon sequestration is controlled by ecosystem structure in the upper ocean." *Frontiers in Earth Science* 11 (2023): 1176196; <https://doi.org/10.3389/feart.2023.1176196>; Pabortsava, K., et al.

"Carbon sequestration in the deep Atlantic enhanced by Saharan dust." *Nature Geoscience* 10.3 (2017): 189-194. <https://doi.org/10.1038/ngeo2899>;

- Presentation for the AtlantECO final scientific conference (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4275504>).
- Outreach: Teach Me in 10 Episode for Technology Networks on sinking microplastics in the Ocean (<https://www.technologynetworks.com/tn/videos/sinking-plastic-snow-how-microplastics-get-to-the-deep-ocean-397187>).

This sub-task also carried out genomic analysis of sinking material collected with sediment traps at the Long-Term Ecological Research site HAUSGARTEN in the Fram Strait, Arctic Ocean.

AWI provided genomic DNA from sinking particle samples collected with long-term sediment traps deployed at around 200 m depth at the Long-Term Ecological Research (LTER) site HAUSGARTEN and as part of the FRAM Infrastructure Program. Sediment traps were deployed at the LTER HAUSGARTEN central station in Fram Strait (79°0'25.92" N, 4°20'3.12" E; Figure 9.3) during four recent annual cycles (2016/17 - 2017/18 - 2018/19 - 2019/21). Each year, 15-20 samples were collected over periods of 7-30 days, covering all seasonal cycles. For these years, corresponding molecular microbial biodiversity data are already available for samples collected in the euphotic zone using automated water samplers (Remote Access Samplers, McLane USA) in parallel to the sediment traps on the same mooring. In total, 51 legacy samples were available for analyses in AtlantECO (Table 9.2). AWI's work included the isolation of genomic DNA for sequencing at Genoscope and measurements of contextual data, e.g. POC flux. The results of the pilot sequencing study, a first batch of 18 samples collected in the period July 2016 – July 2017 were reported as part of deliverable D6.4.2 in 2023. Since then the remaining samples were subjected to 16S and the 18S amplicon sequencing at Genoscope. Furthermore, metagenomes were sequenced for seven samples. Quality assessments and further analyses of these sequences are pending. Alongside with this, measurements of contextual biogeochemical data from the sediment trap samples were accomplished by AWI.

Figure 9.3. (A) Deployment of a sediment trap at LTER HAUSGARTEN HGIV (B) Map of LTER HAUSGARTEN to illustrate the location of deployment.

Subtask activities related to moored sediment trap work in numbers (#cruises; sites; deployments; experiments; samples; analyses; parameters; data).

Cruises of RV Polarstern on which mooring deployment and exchange took place: 2016 – PS99, 2017 – PS107, 2018 – PS114, 2019 – PS121, 2021 – PS136

Samples. Preparation of sediment trap samples performed by AWI included: 1. visual inspection of trap cups, 2. picking of zooplankton (swimmers) under a dissecting microscope, 3. wet-splitting into 1/32 volumetric splits, 4. filtration on 0.22 µm membrane filters, 5. DNA extraction using the DNeasy PowerWater Kit.

In total 51 DNA samples were sent to Genoscope for 16S and 18S amplicon sequencing (Table 9.2). Sequencing was performed using primers Bac 16Sv4v5, 515F/926R (Parada et al. 2016; <https://doi.org/10.1111/1462-2920.13023>) and Euk 18Sv4, 528iF/938iR (Metfies et al. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0233921>). The number of successful amplifications and sequencing runs is: 50 amplicon sequence pairs for bacteria, and 43 amplicon sequence pairs for eukaryotes. A subset of 7 samples were subjected to metagenomic sequencing.

Parameters and Data. All sequencing data will be published in the European Nucleotide Archive (ENA) as part of the AtlantECO umbrella study/project PRJEB78421. The public release data for the LTER HAUSGARTEN legacy data has been set to 2026-09-01.

In addition, contextual biogeochemical data were obtained for all sediment trap samples, in collaboration with colleagues at AWI. This includes:

- POC flux,
- particulate organic nitrogen flux,
- total particulate matter flux,
- calcium carbonate flux,
- dissolved and particulate silica flux.

After quality control, these data will be made publically available at the PANGAEA World Data Center no later than two years after the end of AtlantECO, i.e. 2027-09-01.

Key exploitable results already available in open access (datasets citations, articles citations, other resources)

- All sequencing data will be published in the European Nucleotide Archive (ENA) as part of the AtlantECO umbrella study/project PRJEB78421. The public release data for the LTER HAUSGARTEN legacy data has been set to 2026-09-01.
- Publications: Master Thesis by Ana Carolina Bercini Gusmao (MarMic, Max Planck Institute for Marine Microbiology, University of Bremen): Seasonal variations of free-living and particle-associated microbial communities in Fram Strait, Arctic Ocean (Oct 2024 – March 2025).

Table 9.2. Overview of LTER HAUSGARTEN legacy samples sequenced at Genoscope in the framework of AtlantECO. MetaB – Metabarcoding, Bac – Bacteria/Archaea, Euk – Eukarya, MetaG – Metagenomics.

Sample name (AtlantECO)	collection date begin (yyyy-mm-dd)	collection date end (yyyy-mm-dd)	Latitude	Longitude	Sampling depth (m)	Genoscope ID MetaB Bac (V4V5)	Genoscope ID MetaB Euk (V4)	MetaG
PS99_72-1_Fe vi34_Up01	2016-07-14	2016-07-22	79.00000	4.33280	196	DFC_AAAOST A	DFC_AASOSTA	
PS99_72-1_Fe vi34_Up02	2016-07-22	2016-07-31	79.00000	4.33280	196	DFC_AABOST A	DFC_AATOSTA	
PS99_72-1_Fe vi34_Up03	2016-07-31	2016-08-15	79.00000	4.33280	196	DFC_AACOST A	DFC_AAUOSTA	x
PS99_72-1_Fe vi34_Up04	2016-08-15	2016-08-31	79.00000	4.33280	196	DFC_AADOST A	no data	
PS99_72-1_Fe vi34_Up05	2016-08-31	2016-09-15	79.00000	4.33280	196	DFC_AAEOST A	DFC_ACZOSTA	
PS99_72-1_Fe vi34_Up06	2016-09-15	2016-09-30	79.00000	4.33280	196	DFC_AAFOSTA	DFC_AAXOSTA	x
PS99_72-1_Fe vi34_Up07	2016-09-30	2016-10-31	79.00000	4.33280	196	DFC_AAGOST A	DFC_AAYOSTA	
PS99_72-1_Fe vi34_Up08	2016-10-31	2016-11-30	79.00000	4.33280	196	DFC_AAHOST A	DFC_AAZOSTA	
PS99_72-1_Fe vi34_Up09	2016-11-30	2016-12-31	79.00000	4.33280	196	DFC_AAIOSTA	DFC_AETOSTA	
PS99_72-1_Fe vi34_Up10	2016-12-31	2017-02-28	79.00000	4.33280	196	DFC_AAJOSTA	DFC_ABBOSTA	x
PS99_72-1_Fe vi34_Up11	2017-02-28	2017-03-31	79.00000	4.33280	196	DFC_AAKOST A	DFC_ABCOSTA; DFC_ADBOSTA	
PS99_72-1_Fe vi34_Up12	2017-03-31	2017-04-17	79.00000	4.33280	196	DFC_AALOSTA	no data	x
PS99_72-1_Fe vi34_Up13	2017-04-17	2017-05-04	79.00000	4.33280	196	DFC_AAMOST A	DFC_ABEOSTA	x
PS99_72-1_Fe vi34_Up14	2017-05-04	2017-05-21	79.00000	4.33280	196	DFC_AANOST A	DFC_AEUOSTA	
PS99_72-1_Fe vi34_Up15	2017-05-21	2017-06-08	79.00000	4.33280	196	DFC_AAOOST A	no data	
PS99_72-1_Fe vi34_Up16	2017-06-08	2017-06-25	79.00000	4.33280	196	DFC_AAPOST A	DFC_ABHOSTA	
PS99_72-1_Fe vi34_Up17	2017-06-25	2017-07-07	79.00000	4.33280	196	DFC_AAQOST A	DFC_ABIOSTA	x
PS99_72-1_Fe vi34_Up18	2017-07-07	2017-07-19	79.00000	4.33280	196	DFC_AAROST A	DFC_AEWOSTA	x
PS107_38-1_F evi36_Up01	2017-08-12	2017-08-21	79.00010	4.33370	201	DFC_ABROST A	DFC_ADFOSTA	
PS107_38-1_F evi36_Up02	2017-08-21	2017-08-31	79.00010	4.33370	201	DFC_ABSOST A	DFC_ADGOSTA	
PS107_38-1_F evi36_Up08	2017-10-31	2017-11-30	79.00010	4.33370	201	DFC_ABTOSTA	DFC_AEXOSTA	
PS107_38-1_F evi36_Up09	2017-11-30	2017-12-31	79.00010	4.33370	201	DFC_ABUOST A	DFC_ADIOSTA	
PS107_38-1_F evi36_Up11	2018-01-31	2018-02-28	79.00010	4.33370	201	DFC_ABVOST A	DFC_AEYOSTA	
PS107_38-1_F evi36_Up15	2018-04-30	2018-05-15	79.00010	4.33370	201	DFC_ABWOST A	DFC_ADKOSTA	
PS107_38-1_F evi36_Up16	2018-05-15	2018-05-31	79.00010	4.33370	201	DFC_ABXOST A	DFC_ADLOSTA	
PS107_38-1_F evi36_Up17	2018-05-31	2018-06-15	79.00010	4.33370	201	DFC_AEMOST A	DFC_ADMOSTA	
PS114_06-1_F evi38_Up06	2018-10-15	2018-11-01	79.00032	4.33272	196	DFC_ABZOST A	DFC_AEZOSTA	
PS114_06-1_F evi38_Up07	2018-11-01	2018-12-01	79.00032	4.33272	196	DFC_ACAOST A	DFC_ADOOSTA	

PS114_06-1_F evi38_Up08	2018-12-01	2019-01-01	79.00032	4.33272	196	DFC_ACBOST A	DFC_ADPOSTA	
PS114_06-1_F evi38_Up09	2019-01-01	2019-02-01	79.00032	4.33272	196	DFC_ACBOST A	DFC_AFAOSTA	
PS114_06-1_F evi38_Up010	2019-02-01	2019-03-01	79.00032	4.33272	196	DFC_ACDOST A	DFC_ADROSTA	
PS114_06-1_F evi38_Up11	2019-03-01	2019-03-16	79.00032	4.33272	196	DFC_ACEOST A	DFC_ADSOSTA	
PS114_06-1_F evi38_Up12	2019-03-16	2019-04-01	79.00032	4.33272	196	DFC_ACFOSTA	DFC_ADTOSTA	
PS121_26-3_F evi40_Up01	2019-09-10	2019-10-01	79.00019	4.33069	200	DFC_ACGOST A	DFC_AFBOSTA	
PS121_26-3_F evi40_Up02	2019-10-01	2019-11-01	79.00019	4.33069	200	DFC_ACHOST A	DFC_ADVOSTA	
PS121_26-3_F evi40_Up03	2019-11-01	2019-12-01	79.00019	4.33069	200	DFC_ACIOSTA	DFC_ADWOSTA	
PS121_26-3_F evi40_Up04	2019-12-01	2020-03-01	79.00019	4.33069	200	DFC_ACJOSTA	DFC_ADXOSTA	
PS121_26-3_F evi40_Up05	2020-03-01	2020-04-01	79.00019	4.33069	200	DFC_ACKOST A	DFC_AFCOSTA	
PS121_26-3_F evi40_Up06	2020-04-01	2020-05-01	79.00019	4.33069	200	DFC_ACLOSTA	DFC_ADZOSTA	
PS121_26-3_F evi40_Up07	2020-05-01	2020-06-01	79.00019	4.33069	200	DFC_AENOST A	no data	
PS121_26-3_F evi40_Up08	2020-06-01	2020-07-01	79.00019	4.33069	200	DFC_ACNOST A	DFC_AEBOSTA	
PS121_26-3_F evi40_Up09	2020-07-01	2020-07-16	79.00019	4.33069	200	no data	no data	
PS121_26-3_F evi40_Up10	2020-07-16	2020-08-01	79.00019	4.33069	200	DFC_AEPOSTA	no data	
PS121_26-3_F evi40_Up11	2020-08-01	2020-09-01	79.00019	4.33069	200	DFC_AEQOST A	no data	
PS121_26-3_F evi40_Up12	2020-09-01	2020-10-01	79.00019	4.33069	200	DFC_AEROSTA	no data	
PS121_26-3_F evi40_Up13	2020-10-01	2020-11-01	79.00019	4.33069	200	DFC_ACSOST A	DFC_AEGOSTA	
PS121_26-3_F evi40_Up14	2020-11-01	2020-12-01	79.00019	4.33069	200	DFC_ACTOSTA	DFC_AEHOSTA	
PS121_26-3_F evi40_Up15	2020-12-01	2021-03-01	79.00019	4.33069	200	DFC_ACIUST A	DFC_AEIOSTA	
PS121_26-3_F evi40_Up16	2021-03-01	2021-04-01	79.00019	4.33069	200	DFC_ACVOST A	DFC_AFIOSTA	
PS121_26-3_F evi40_Up17	2021-04-01	2021-05-01	79.00019	4.33069	200	DFC_ACWOS TA	DFC_AEKOSTA	
PS121_26-3_F evi40_Up18	2021-05-01	2021-06-01	79.00019	4.33069	200	DFC_ACXOST A	DFC_AELOSTA	

10 Synergies with third party sampling programmes (lead: EMBL)

AtlantECO actively fostered collaboration with major international oceanographic programmes to expand its spatial coverage, enhance methodological harmonisation, and strengthen comparative analyses across contrasting Atlantic and Southern Ocean systems. Through coordinated sampling, shared protocols (including eDNA and microbiome approaches), and data exchange agreements, these partnerships provided access to high-resolution physical, biogeochemical, and biological observations beyond AtlantECO-dedicated cruises. The integration of third-party datasets significantly improved basin-scale assessments of plankton diversity, ecosystem functioning, and environmental drivers, reinforcing the project's capacity to link regional process studies with large-scale microbiome and biogeochemical patterns.

RV Antea (France) - Amazon plume study

During 28 August–8 October 2021, the French research vessel Antea conducted the AMAZOMIX oceanographic campaign in the western tropical Atlantic, focusing on the dynamics of the Amazon River plume and its interaction with shelf and open-ocean processes. Operating from Cayenne (French Guiana) and in coordination with Brazilian authorities, the cruise surveyed the continental shelf break and adjacent oceanic waters influenced by freshwater discharge, strong stratification, and mesoscale to submesoscale circulation features.

The primary objective was to investigate how fine-scale physical processes (fronts, turbulent mixing, and current instabilities) structure plankton communities and regulate biogeochemical fluxes within the plume-influenced system. The multidisciplinary approach combined high-resolution CTD profiling, turbulence measurements, acoustic and optical observations, water sampling for nutrient and isotopic analyses, and biological collections spanning microorganisms to mesozooplankton. Autonomous platforms and moored instrumentation complemented ship-based observations, enabling improved spatial and temporal resolution.

AMAZOMIX also addressed the distribution and trophic transfer of contaminants, including trace metals and microplastics, within plume waters. The campaign contributed valuable process-oriented data on ecosystem functioning at the interface between riverine inputs and the open Atlantic, providing important context for basin-scale microbiome and biogeochemical investigations conducted under AtlantECO.

RV Houssay (Argentina) - Coccolithophore bloom study

The RV Houssay, formally known as *Motovelero Bernardo Houssay*, is owned and run by the *Prefectura Naval Argentina*, a security force with similarities to the US Coast Guard. A team of local scientists sailed onboard RV Houssay in November 2021 from Ushuaia to Buenos Aires to study the pre-bloom stage of the coccolithophore *Emiliana huxleyi* along the continental shelf-break. This was done in coordination with *Tara* that sailed later in December 2021 to sample the bloom (see corresponding section above). Samples were taken at 10 stations, four on the shelf, four on the slope and two in an off-shore eddy (open ocean east of the shelf) carrying a coccolithophore bloom. Different plankton groups were aimed through nets and Niskin bottles, covering from picoplankton to mesozooplankton. Grazing experiments were performed in 8 of the 10 stations. Samples of plankton groups have already been analysed in laboratories and plankton abundances are ready to be used together with several environmental variables.

RV Polarstern (Germany) - Southern Ocean study

The Antarctic RV Polarstern expedition PS129 from March to April 2022 covered a transect from the Neumayer Station III across the Weddell Sea between Kapp Norvegia and the tip of the Antarctic Peninsula (Hybrid Antarctic Float Observation System transect), with two excursions to the south (Figure 10.1, insert). PS129 observed and sampled hydrography, nutrients, dissolved oxygen, carbon dioxide, dissolved and particulate organic carbon, bacterial and microalgal strains. eDNA samples were taken throughout the expedition

according to the AtlantEco protocol from the CTD and an underway pump. During PS129, RV Polarstern encountered and samples a massive icealgal bloom accumulating in sloshy ice forming at the surface (Figure 10.2). Genomic sequencing will afford the characterization of phyto- and bacterioplankton along a wide transect through the Weddell Sea and enable a comparison of the biodiversity at stations that were visited by the expedition in the austral summer and then in austral autumn by PS129.

Figure 10.1. Ice-algal bloom in the Weddell Sea during expedition PS129.

RV Algoa (South Africa) - Benguela ecosystem study

The South African Department of Forestry, Fisheries and the Environment (DFFE) has been deploying the RV Algoa in the Southern Benguela upwelling region as part of the Integrated Ecosystem Programme (IEP). The IEP's objective is to measure relevant changes in biodiversity, ecosystem function and the services they provide. This is carried out through long term monitoring of the SBUS in the form of 44 stations (four transects) on a seasonal basis. UCT has been contributing to this programme by sampling the SBUS microbiome seasonally since 2016. Genomic (metaG & metaB) and flow cytometry samples were taken in August (Austral winter) 2022-2023 and November (austral spring) of 2022. There is a planned cruise on the SAMBA mooring line (Figure 10.2) this Sept-Oct where they will take additional samples (E-W transect at 34.5 deg S from Cape Town to 15 deg E), as well as the Nov 2023 and Feb 2024 IEP cruises. Samples will be extracted and sequenced following Genoscope protocols.

Figure 10.2. CTD stations for the SAMBA line

RV Thalassa (France) - SCOPES Senegal upwelling study

The SCOPES campaign (Structuration des Communautés Planctoniques en réponse à la dynamique de l'upwelling sud-Sénégalais) carried out in Senegalese waters from December 18, 2022 to January 5, 2023 aimed to partly fill science gaps by acquiring new information on plankton communities in relation to the dynamics at the key time of the return of the upwelling season in the SCCUS. Plankton constitutes the main diet of planktivorous SPF. Hence biogeochemistry and hydrodynamics define together their habitats and influence their growth, reproduction, mortality and distribution. This important sample collection performed by 45 scientists involved in seven laboratories in France and three in Senegal will allow a major step forward in the understanding and quantification of plankton dynamics. We propose to elucidate together the role of physical processes in the establishment of the ecosystem of the upwelling season which differs from that of the monsoon season.

During SCOPES, we acquired new information on the plankton communities in relation to the dynamics of the region. A special effort was made to observe a maximum number of variables continuously along the vessel's trajectory. These continuous observations were collected to: 1- characterise synoptically the first 100 metres of the water column; 2- identify spatial transitions; 3- contextualise the sampling stations. Temperature, salinity, dissolved oxygen, nitrate concentration, fluorescence, and turbidity were measured in the first 100 metres along the trajectory from a towed fish (Scanfish; ~2500 profiles). Temperature, salinity, dissolved oxygen data were acquired at the surface from the thermosalinograph. Phytoplankton communities were continuously observed using the ship's ferrybox (including the Algal Online Analyser), a flow cytometer and a Fast Repetition Rate fluorometer (indicating the level of photosynthetic activity of the algae). The pCO_2 was also observed continuously. Information on upper trophic levels was collected from fisheries echosounders. The main organisms present, including zooplankton and bladder fish, can be differentiated from the echosounders operating at six different emission frequencies on FRV Thalassa (18, 38, 70, 120, 200 & 333 kHz). In the northern part of the SPF nursery ground (southern Senegalese shelf), egg abundance was observed from the CUFES (Continuous Underway Fish Egg Sampler) mounted on Thalassa's hull.

46 CTD stations completed the observation of the water column by measuring temperature and salinity, dissolved oxygen, light intensity, nitrate concentration (SUNA), phytoplankton (BBE fluoroprobe, multispectral fluorometer) and zooplankton (Underwater Vision Profiler 5 + Acoustic Zooplankton Fish Profiler) diversity and particle size distribution (LISST Optical Laser diffraction instrument). Water samples were collected from the main water bodies of interest. Nutrients, particulate organic matter and dissolved organic matter are measured. Taxonomic and functional diversity of plankton (phytoplankton, microzooplankton, mesozooplankton and gelatinous) will be studied through various approaches (flux cytometry, pigments by HPLC, microscopic taxonomy, metagenomics DNA & RNA (147 filters), image processing). Their quality will be studied through their fatty acid composition. Fluxes will be given by the measurements of primary (C^{13} incubations, FRRf) and secondary production (counting nauplii) and by the particle size spectra.

The ocean circulation encountered during SCOPES is given by the hull ADCPs and six moorings deployed before and during the campaign (Fig. 10.3). Finally, one ARVOR-O2 and one ARVOR-BGC were deployed at the edge of the southern continental slope and thus add to the two ARVORs deployed in 2021 located in the study region during SCOPES.

Figure 10.3. Map of Sea Surface Temperature (SST) measured by VIIRS on January 1st 2023. The white solid line represents the ship track of FRV Thalassa between 17 December 2022 and 5 January 2023. Acoustic data were recorded along the whole ship track as well as Cytosense, Fluoroprobe and FRRf surface data. Around 2500 profiles between the surface and 100 m depth were also collected along ship track during the 127 hours of Scanfish towing. 46 CTD stations were carried out (locations indicated by double lines circles). Water was sampled at different depths from the 24 Niskin bottles on board the rosette frame for analyses detailed in the table above. Large plankton organisms were also sampled with different nets (WP2, Multinet) and micronekton was sampled with a fishing net (14 deployments). Hundreds of microstructure profiles were also acquired to quantify vertical micro-turbulence.

11 Coastal and open-ocean plankton studies (lead: USP)

The Oceanographic Institute of the University of São Paulo (IOUSP), co-leader of WP4, conducted multiple investigations on plankton dynamics along the Brazilian continental margin and in the Gulf of Mexico within the framework of the AtlantECO project. These studies focused on resolving fine-scale biological patterns and their coupling with physical oceanographic processes.

The core biological observations were based on high-resolution, in situ digital imaging. This included the use of commercially available instruments (Underwater Vision Profilers), as well as imaging systems developed in-house at USP (shadowgraphic camera) and by a partner institution, Florida Atlantic University (FAU, USA), namely the HOLOCAM digital holographic system.

Together, these complementary imaging approaches enabled detailed characterization of plankton abundance, vertical distribution, particle size spectra, and biophysical interactions across contrasting hydrographic regimes. This Section summarises the main scientific achievements resulting from these activities.

Flow-topography interactions drive zooplankton abundance and carbon export to depth along the Vitória-Trindade Seamount Chain (Southwestern Atlantic)

The ILHAS1 cruise (R/V Alpha Crucis, January–February 2017) investigated how physical oceanographic structures, particularly the Vitória Eddy (VE) and seamount topography, regulate zooplankton communities and carbon export along the Vitória–Trindade Seamount Chain (VTC) in the southwestern Atlantic (Fig. 11.1). Sampling along two zonal transects revealed that stations simultaneously influenced by the VE and seamounts supported zooplankton abundances up to four times higher than offshore, oligotrophic stations, with elevated particulate organic carbon (POC) fluxes exceeding $200 \text{ mg C m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$ in eddy-influenced surface waters. Rather than classical seamount-induced upwelling, the dominant physical drivers were eddy deformation and flow–topography interactions, which enhanced vertical mixing and chlorophyll-a accumulation at subsurface depths. Contrary to expectations, an isolated seamount effect on zooplankton was not detected. Rhizaria, often undersampled by traditional net methods, numerically dominated the community (up to 79% of abundance), underscoring the value of optical in situ profiling. Normalized biovolume size spectra (Fig. 11.2) confirmed higher trophic transfer efficiency near the shelf and in eddy-influenced waters, while offshore stations displayed size spectra consistent with near-steady-state oligotrophic conditions. These results demonstrate that the biological pump efficiency in the VTC region is primarily governed by the interplay between mesoscale eddy dynamics, seamount topography, and lateral shelf inputs.

Subtask Activities — Key Numbers

- **Cruises / Transects:** 1 oceanographic cruise (ILHAS1); 2 quasi-zonal transects (TI and TII)
- **Sampling sites / stations:** 37 vertical profile stations (Table 11.1)
- **Instrument deployments:** 37 CTD-rosette casts; 37 UVP5 (Underwater Vision Profiler 5) deployments
- **Station groups:** 4 (A: eddy+seamount, n=8; B: seamount-only, n=10; C: oceanic, n=11; D: eddy-only, n=10)

- **Samples / profiles:** 37 hydrographic profiles (0–1,000 m); discrete Niskin bottle samples for chlorophyll-a calibration
- **Analyses:** Zooplankton taxonomic classification (EcoTaxa/Zooprocess, Random Forest + manual validation); particle size spectra (EcoPart, 25 size bins, 102 μm –26 mm ESD); NBSS linear regressions per station; POC flux estimations (250–1,500 μm ESD); ANOSIM, Kruskal-Wallis, and Dunn post-hoc statistical tests
- **Parameters measured:** Conservative temperature, absolute salinity, potential density, dissolved oxygen, chlorophyll-a fluorescence (calibrated), zooplankton abundance, biovolume, taxonomic composition (9 groups), NBSS slope and intercept, POC vertical flux
- **Data depth layers:** 4 (Mixed Layer, Seasonal Thermocline, Permanent Thermocline, Below Permanent Thermocline)

Key Exploitable Results — Already Available in Open Access

- Zooplankton image classification platform: **EcoTaxa** (ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr) and **EcoPart**, publicly accessible repositories used for all UVP5 data processing and storage

Key Exploitable Results — To Be Available in Open Access

- A manuscript reporting all findings from the ILHAS1 cruise, including zooplankton community structure, NBSS analysis, POC flux estimates, and flow–topography coupling along the VTC, is currently in the final stages of preparation for submission to *Deep-Sea Research Part I*, under the open access agreement between the University of São Paulo and Elsevier, ensuring free public availability upon acceptance;
- Full UVP5 zooplankton and particle datasets from the ILHAS1 cruise will be made publicly available through the EcoTaxa and EcoPart open platforms upon manuscript publication;
- Processed hydrographic (CTD) data from the 37 stations will be deposited in an open repository (e.g., SEANOE or Pangaea) concurrent with manuscript publication

Figure 11.1. The Vitória-Trindade Seamount Chain (VTC) domain; main geological features are numbered in green, a few locations of interest are named inside the map. The Vitoria Eddy (VE), Abrolhos Eddy (AE) and the southern branch of the South Equatorial Current (sSEC) are represented by black arrows, the Brazil Current (BC) as red arrows, and the Intermediate Western Boundary Current (IWBC) in blue arrows. The station groups (see section 2.3) are presented by small circles: group A (pink; eddy and seamount influence), group B (blue; seamount influence only), group C (gray; oceanic stations) and group D (orange; eddy influence).

Figure 11.2. Normalized Biovolume Size Spectra (NBSS) for all the stations sampled along the Vitória-Trindade Seamount Chain (VTC), grouped by colors, and superimposed by the average slope fitted for each group.

Table 11.1. Sampling stations included in this study, with station identifier (Station), geographic coordinates (Latitude, Longitude), and date and time of data acquisition (Sampling date and time, UTC).

Station	Location	Datetime
S0318	20°03'42.01"S, 38°08'17.41"W	2017-02-02 01:57:28
S0319	20°18'17.39"S, 38°07'54.59"W	2017-02-02 07:18:04
S0320	20°30'16.81"S, 38°08'17.41"W	2017-02-02 11:32:33
S0321	20°11'04.20"S, 37°38'57.01"W	2017-02-02 19:27:17
S0322	20°33'11.99"S, 37°13'42.60"W	2017-02-03 02:07:23
S0323	20°21'05.40"S, 36°40'53.40"W	2017-02-03 14:57:37
S0346	21°07'54.01"S, 36°41'13.81"W	2017-02-11 09:13:55
S0349	21°08'00.60"S, 37°45'19.19"W	2017-02-11 18:47:25
S0324	20°28'01.81"S, 35°59'28.21"W	2017-02-03 22:56:09
S0325	20°33'38.99"S, 35°20'59.39"W	2017-02-04 07:59:31
S0326	20°39'16.20"S, 34°44'50.39"W	2017-02-04 17:24:19
S0327	20°37'52.21"S, 34°12'13.21"W	2017-02-05 00:36:51
S0328	20°38'20.40"S, 33°28'34.21"W	2017-02-05 11:40:18
S0342	21°07'40.80"S, 34°30'10.80"W	2017-02-10 13:36:49
S0343	21°07'57.00"S, 35°25'03.00"W	2017-02-10 20:47:16
S0344	21°07'54.01"S, 36°19'37.81"W	2017-02-11 03:36:04
S0329	20°39'54.61"S, 32°52'37.81"W	2017-02-05 21:35:48
S0330	20°38'16.80"S, 32°12'31.21"W	2017-02-06 05:49:27
S0331	20°39'32.40"S, 31°36'46.19"W	2017-02-06 18:48:09
S0332	20°38'41.39"S, 30°48'34.81"W	2017-02-07 04:36:02
S0333	20°38'24.00"S, 29°55'27.59"W	2017-02-07 15:15:26
S0334	20°36'42.01"S, 29°12'52.81"W	2017-02-08 00:23:03
S0335	20°37'23.41"S, 28°18'15.01"W	2017-02-08 07:56:53
S0337	21°08'07.80"S, 29°55'07.21"W	2017-02-08 22:03:22
S0338	21°08'03.01"S, 30°49'57.00"W	2017-02-09 09:14:03
S0339	21°07'52.21"S, 31°44'29.40"W	2017-02-09 16:01:59

S0340	21°07'50.99"S, 32°39'52.81"W	2017-02-09 23:04:10
S0351	21°07'49.80"S, 38°27'59.40"W	2017-02-12 01:30:34
S0352	21°07'52.21"S, 38°49'45.59"W	2017-02-12 05:20:42
S0353	21°07'53.40"S, 39°11'15.00"W	2017-02-12 08:39:53
S0354	21°08'13.81"S, 39°33'36.00"W	2017-02-12 13:28:35
S0355	21°07'55.20"S, 39°54'20.99"W	2017-02-12 17:41:09
S0356	21°07'43.79"S, 40°01'25.21"W	2017-02-12 19:52:47
S0357	21°07'34.21"S, 40°04'50.99"W	2017-02-12 22:41:25
S0358	21°07'25.79"S, 40°08'28.21"W	2017-02-13 00:04:33
S0359	21°07'54.01"S, 40°12'08.39"W	2017-02-13 03:28:34
S0360	21°07'41.41"S, 40°15'07.81"W	2017-02-13 04:43:11
S0318	20°03'42.01"S, 38°08'17.41"W	2017-02-02 01:57:28
S0319	20°18'17.39"S, 38°07'54.59"W	2017-02-02 07:18:04
S0320	20°30'16.81"S, 38°08'17.41"W	2017-02-02 11:32:33
S0321	20°11'04.20"S, 37°38'57.01"W	2017-02-02 19:27:17

UVP and CTD Metadata organization - Mission Microbiomes

This task focused on the organization, quality control, and public dissemination of a structured oceanographic imaging dataset derived from vertical profiling surveys carried out with the Underwater Vision Profiler and CTDs during the Mission Microbiomes topical studies (Fig. 11.3). Activities included comprehensive metadata standardization, covering sampling information, geolocation, acquisition parameters, instrument configuration, and cruise-level descriptors. Quality-control procedures were implemented to verify data completeness and to detect inconsistencies. The curated dataset (Table 11.2) has been uploaded to the EcoTaxa platform, resulting in 319 vertical stations, where images are currently undergoing systematic manual validation to guarantee taxonomic reliability and accurate particle classification. This validation step enhances the robustness of size-structured and biogeochemical analyses derived from the dataset. By adhering to FAIR data principles and enabling open-access dissemination through EcoTaxa, this effort ensures transparency, reproducibility, and long-term reusability. The organized dataset provides a solid foundation for ongoing and future studies on the Atlantic plankton dynamics and carbon cycling, strengthening the project's overall scientific impact and data legacy.

Activities — Key Numbers

- 319 UVP5 vertical profiles freely available on Ecotaxa;
- Check all available logsheets to associate field observations with the UVP profiles.

Key Exploitable Results

- Manual validation of 319 UVP5 vertical profiles, freely available on Ecotaxa;
- 1 manuscript currently in preparation using a subset of this dataset, focusing on the Amazon River Plume.

Figure 11.3. Sampling location of the entire dataset from both campaigns. Scatters represent the sampling location with colors representing a first exploratory analysis of abundance (individuals m^{-3}).

Table 11.2. Total of UVP5 profiles available on Ecotaxa, grouped by Campaigns.

Campaign	Profiles Available
Martinique-Macapa	47
Macapá-Belém	2
Belém-Salvador-Bahia	9
King George Island-Punta-Arenas	21
Punta Arenas-CapeTown	39
Walvis-Bay-Pointe-Noire	37
PointeNoire-Banjul	6
Banjul-Dakar	16

Salvador-Rio	2
Punta-Arenas-Puerto-Montt	38
Puerto-Montt-Concepción	46
Concepción-Valparaíso	30
Valparaíso-Iquique	26

Amazon River Plume study

This study investigates the particulate organic carbon (POC) dynamics associated with the Amazon River plume by integrating imaging observations and physical modeling approaches. The study first characterizes the composition and size structure of plume-associated POC using high-resolution image data acquired with the Underwater Vision Profiler (UVP5) on board Tara (Fig. 11.4), providing detailed insights into particle types, biovolume distribution, and vertical structure across plume-influenced waters. To identify regions of enhanced carbon export to the mesopelagic layer, Lagrangian particle tracking simulations were coupled with a regional hydrodynamic model. This framework enables the quantification of both vertical export pathways and lateral transport, linking biological particle fields to physical circulation patterns. Particular emphasis is placed on understanding how regional processes, including plume and mesoscale variability, and boundary current dynamics, modulate POC retention and export efficiency.

Key Numbers

- Manual validation of 15 vertical profiles from the Martinique-Macapá campaign;
- Development of observation oriented Lagrangian analysis, incorporating UVP5 features into a Lagrangian numerical experiment.

Key Exploitable Results

- 10-years of Lagrangian analysis output on Zenodo or Seanoec;
- 1 manuscript currently in preparation for submission as open access using agreement of University of São Paulo with Wiley or Elsevier.

Figure 11.4. (left) Plain view of sea surface salinity in colors (given in PSU), with the 32 PSU (thin black), 33 PSU (solid white) and 35.25 PSU (dashed white) isohalines and the sampling sites used in this study. (right) Plain view of sea surface anomaly in colors (given in meters) and geostrophic currents in black vectors: the size of the vector corresponds to the intensity. Bullets are the sampling locations used in this study.

High-Resolution Temporal Dynamics of Diatoms in a Large and Well-Mixed Tropical Estuary

Phytoplankton in tropical coastal systems respond to a complex interplay of tidal, meteorological, and hydrological forces that traditional sampling cannot resolve. This study deployed a custom shadowgraphic imaging system at the mouth of Baía de Todos os Santos (BTS), Brazil, the third largest tropical bay in the South Atlantic, collecting microphytoplankton images every 30 minutes over 20 months (November 2020 to June 2022). Seven diatom taxa were automatically identified and quantified using a convolutional neural network (CNN) classifier achieving 98.5% accuracy, generating one of the highest-resolution phytoplankton time series reported for a tropical estuary.

Frequency-domain analysis revealed that distinct environmental drivers govern diatom dynamics at different temporal scales (Fig. 11.5). At sub-daily scales, solar radiation emerged as the dominant control, with diatom peaks lagging light maxima by 3–20 hours depending on taxon. At intermediate (53 h–13 days) to monthly scales, water temperature, dissolved oxygen, salinity, and subtidal sea level were the principal structuring forces. A clear ecological dichotomy emerged between r-strategist coastal taxa (*Coscinodiscus wailesii*, *Bacteriastrium*–*Chaetoceros* complex, and *Guinardia striata*), which peaked during spring tides coinciding with enhanced river discharge and nutrient input, and K-strategist marine taxa such as *Rhizosolenia robusta* and the *Rhizosolenia*–*Proboscia* complex, which reached maximum densities during neap tides when oligotrophic oceanic water intrusions into the bay were strongest (Fig. 11.6). The alternation of these functional groups across the neap–spring tidal cycle illustrates how physical forcing structures biological community composition in estuaries, with implications for bloom monitoring, harmful algal species management, and the bioindicator potential of diatom assemblages under shifting hydrological regimes driven by climate change and anthropogenic pressures such as dam regulation.

Subtask Activities — Key Numbers

- 1 deployment site: moored imaging system at Salver Harbour (Bahia), at the Baía de Todos os Santos (~6 meter depth), fixed at 1 m below the water surface;
- 1 long-term mooring deployment: continuous operation from 04 November 2020 to 10 June 2022 (20 months)
- ~100 million Regions of Interest (ROIs) extracted from raw imaging sequences across the deployment period
- ~29,000 imaging cycles completed (one every 30 min; 175–180 frames per cycle; 101.7 mL imaged volume per frame)
- 7 microdiatom taxa identified and quantified: *Coscinodiscus wailesii*, *Bacteriastrum*–*Chaetoceros* complex, *Skeletonema*–*Guinardia* complex, *Guinardia striata*, *Hemidiscus* sp., *Rhizosolenia robusta*, and *Rhizosolenia*–*Proboscica* complex
- 2 hierarchical CNN classifiers trained: first-stage: 5 classes (phytoplankton, zooplankton, multiples, detritus, unfocused); second-stage: 7 diatom taxa + detritus/unfocused; overall accuracy 98.54%, F1 macro score 98.54%
- 14 environmental parameters monitored at 30-min resolution: temperature, salinity, dissolved oxygen, CDOM, total/tidal/subtidal sea level, river discharge, N–S and E–W current velocity, N–S and E–W wind velocity, rainfall, solar radiation
- 4 frequency bands analysed – high frequency (<53 h), low frequency (53 h–13 days), neap–spring (13–15 days), and monthly (≥ 15 days)
- Multiple statistical analyses applied: spectral analysis, Lanczos FIR filtering, cross-correlation (CC), Transfer Entropy (TE), Redundancy Analysis (RDA), canonical correspondence analysis (CCA), multiple linear regression (MLR), Mann–Whitney U tests

Key Exploitable Results — Already Available in Open Access

- Birocchi P. et al. (2026). High-resolution temporal dynamics of diatoms in a large and well-mixed tropical estuary. *Marine Environmental Research*, 215, 107807. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marenvres.2025.107807> — Full open-access article (CC BY 4.0) reporting all methods, results, and discussion.

Figure 11.5. Time series of microdiatom densities (ind L⁻¹) obtained with the moored system from November 04, 2020 to June 10, 2022 for (a) *Coscinodiscus wailesii* (COS), (b) *Bacteriastrum-Chaetoceros* complex (BACCHAE), (c) *Skeletonema-Guinardia* complex (SKEGUI), (d) *Guinardia striata* (GUISTRI), (e) *Hemidiscus* sp. (HEMI), (f) *Rhizosolenia robusta* (RHIRO), and (g) *Rhizosolenia-Proboscia* complex (RHIPRO). Note the scale breaks in SKEGUI, BACCHAE, and GUISTRI.

Figure 11.6. Graphical abstract with an example of the 7 microdiatom on the left, a schematic of the main results in the middle and a schematic of the tides effect on the population dynamics on the right.

Characterization of the vertical distribution of plankton and the formation of thin layers in the northern Gulf of Mexico using digital holography

This study investigates how hydrographic structure associated with the Mississippi River (MR) plume regulates the vertical distribution of plankton and promotes thin phytoplankton layer formation in the northern Gulf of Mexico. During a cruise in May 2017, five stations were sampled using an integrated instrumentation suite combining high-resolution CTD profiling, optical sensors, satellite observations, and an in situ digital holographic imaging system (HOLOCAM) (Fig. 11.7).

Figure 11.7. The instrumentation package deployed in the Gulf of Mexico (GoM) with the relevant instruments labelled, and sampling locations (closed circles) in the northern Gulf of Mexico (nGoM).

Satellite imagery revealed strong short-term variability in plume extent, while hydrographic profiles identified distinct water mass regimes, including plume-core, plume-edge mixing, shelf saline, and offshore oligotrophic waters. At plume-edge stations, dense shelf water intruded beneath buoyant freshwater, forming bottom-trapped saline wedges and compressed pycnoclines.

Thin phytoplankton layers were repeatedly detected at or immediately above these density interfaces. These layers were 1.2–3.5 m thick and exhibited chlorophyll-a concentrations up to threefold higher than background levels. The assemblage was dominated by chain-forming diatoms, particularly *Chaetoceros debilis* and *C. socialis*. In contrast, zooplankton (copepods, appendicularians, and nauplii) were broadly distributed throughout the upper water column and showed limited aggregation within chlorophyll maxima, suggesting weak short-term trophic coupling. Examples of high-resolution, reconstructed holographic images are shown in Figure 11.8.

Figure 11.8. Reconstructed images of some of the most abundant taxa in the study region, obtained after segmentation, reconstruction and automatic classification.

Chlorophyll concentration and stratification intensity were primary drivers of community structure across stations. Results support the hypothesis that mesoscale plume–shelf interactions and salt-wedge dynamics create physical trapping mechanisms that organize phytoplankton into thin layers, while zooplankton responses remain decoupled at the temporal scales resolved.

This work demonstrates the value of digital holography coupled with hydrographic and satellite observations for resolving fine-scale biophysical interactions in river-influenced continental shelves.

Activities — Key Numbers

- Cruises / Sampling period: 1 oceanographic cruise (May 5–12, 2017) in the northern Gulf of Mexico
- Sampling sites / stations: 5 stations; 13 vertical profile events (some stations revisited)
- Instrument deployments: 13 HOLOCAM (digital holographic imaging) vertical profiles; 13 CTD casts (Sea-Bird FastCAT); 13 WETLabs ac-s optical sensor deployments
- Station groups (hydrographic regimes): 4 (Plume-core; Plume-edge mixing; Shelf saline waters; Offshore oligotrophic waters)
- Samples / profiles: 13 hydrographic profiles (surface to maximum station depth, up to ~1,000 m at offshore station); holographic imaging on downcasts and upcasts (15,370 holograms; ~40.7 L total imaged volume)
- Analyses:
 - Hologram detection and reconstruction (Angular Spectrum Algorithm)
 - ROI segmentation with morphological operators
 - CNN feature extraction (InceptionResNet)
 - Dimensionality reduction (t-SNE) and expert validation
 - Thin layer identification (≤ 5 m thickness; ≥ 1.3 – $3\times$ chlorophyll background)
 - Brunt–Väisälä frequency (N) calculation
 - Kruskal–Wallis and Dunn post-hoc tests
 - Redundancy Analysis (RDA; 4 environmental variables \times 15 taxa; Hellinger transformation)
- Parameters measured: Conservative temperature, salinity, potential density, chlorophyll-a (ac-s absorption line height method), satellite-derived chlorophyll-a, SST, enhanced RGB composites, plankton abundance (particles L^{-1}), taxonomic composition (phytoplankton and zooplankton groups), vertical distribution patterns, thin layer thickness, chlorophyll enhancement ratios
- Data depth layers: Three analytical depth strata (surface ~10 m; intermediate ~20 m; bottom >30 m), plus fine-scale vertical resolution for thin layer detection (meter-scale)

Key Exploitable Results

- Digital holography processing workflow (HOLOCAM reconstruction, CNN-based feature extraction, t-SNE clustering) based on previously published open methodologies;
- R statistical scripts and satellite image processing routines (R v4.3.2; vegan, ggplot2, patchwork packages) reproducible under open-source frameworks;
- Foundational HOLOCAM methodological pipeline available from the study (see next point).
- A manuscript reporting all findings on plume–shelf interaction, salt-wedge dynamics, thin layer formation, and plankton vertical distribution in the northern Gulf of Mexico is in the second round of revisions in a peer-reviewed oceanographic journal, Marine Ecology Progress Series, with open-access publication ensuring unrestricted availability in case of acceptance;
- The processed holographic plankton dataset (15,370 holograms; classified ROIs; abundance matrices per depth bin) will be made publicly accessible in an appropriate marine data repository upon publication;
- Associated hydrographic and chlorophyll datasets (CTD, ac-s derived chlorophyll-a, and satellite products used for plume characterization) will be deposited in an open repository (e.g., SEANOE, PANGAEA, or equivalent) concurrent with manuscript publication.

12 Conclusion

This deliverable documents the extensive effort undertaken within AtlantECO Work Package 4 to generate augmented observations of Atlantic microbiomes, plastics and the plastisphere, in full alignment with the project's overarching objectives.

Across flagship expeditions, coordinated basin-wide sampling events, long-term monitoring lines, citizen-science initiatives and third-party collaborations, AtlantECO achieved an unprecedented spatial and temporal coverage of the Atlantic Ocean, from the Arctic and subpolar North Atlantic to the Southern Ocean, and from coastal river plumes and estuaries to oligotrophic gyres and deep waters.

Data acquisition spanned multiple years and seasons, capturing contrasting hydrographic regimes, upwelling systems, mesoscale and submesoscale structures, and highly dynamic river-influenced environments. This temporal replication and environmental breadth are essential to disentangle natural variability from long-term change, particularly in regions experiencing strong climatic and anthropogenic pressures.

A defining strength of the programme has been its integrative, multidisciplinary approach. Standardised protocols were applied across platforms to combine genomics (amplicon, metagenomic and metatranscriptomic sequencing), high-resolution imaging, biogeochemical measurements, contaminant and microplastic analyses, sediment trap time series, and atmospheric sampling. The harmonisation enabled through the AtlantECO Handbook of Standards and Best Practices ensured inter-comparability of datasets across continents and institutions, reinforcing the robustness of downstream analyses and modelling activities.

The success of this effort relied on the coordinated engagement of numerous institutions from Europe, Brazil and South Africa, together with partners across the wider Atlantic basin. Research vessels, sailing yachts, fixed observatories and citizen platforms were mobilised in a coherent observational framework, strengthening North-South collaboration and capacity building. Sequencing centres, imaging hubs and analytical laboratories worked in synergy to process, curate and make data openly accessible in accordance with the project's Data Management Plan.

Collectively, these augmented observations constitute one of the most comprehensive microbiome-focused datasets ever assembled for the Atlantic Ocean. They provide the empirical foundation required to assess ecosystem structure and function, evaluate the impacts of plastics and other stressors, and improve predictive eco-socio-economic models. Beyond the project lifetime, this legacy of harmonised, open-access data and strengthened international collaboration will remain a cornerstone for future Atlantic research and sustainable ocean governance.

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